

D6.4 Label-based marketing strategies for food products derived from OHM and OVs

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LiveSeeding - Organic seed and plant breeding to accelerate sustainable and diverse food systems in Europe is a 4-year Innovation Action funded by the European Union, the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI). The project started in October 2022 and brings together 37 organisations operating in 16 European countries. LiveSeeding provides science-based evidence and best practice solutions to help achieve 100 % organic seed.

LiveSeeding contributes to the transition towards environmentally friendly, climate-neutral, healthy and fair food systems through a **PUSH-PULL-ENABLE strategy** to

- enhance the availability and adequacy of organic seeds of cultivars appropriate to organic farming (PUSH),
- increase and stabilise the market demand for organic seeds of cultivars appropriate to organic farming (PULL),
- foster an enabling policy and regulatory environment where both demand and supply can harmoniously and productively negotiate without irrelevant constraints due to legal restrictions and/or regulatory fragmentation (ENABLE).

LiveSeeding addresses the topics in a **holistic multi-actor, multi-stakeholder, participatory approach** involving stakeholders along the value chain in 17 local **Living Labs (LLs)** and 3 established networks of organic breeders (**ECO-PB**), seed

savers (**ECLLD**) and Milan Urban Food Policy Pact (**MUFPP**). 15 European countries cover the different pedoclimatic zones and socio-economic contexts, including countries with a low level of development in organic seed and breeding in Eastern and Southern Europe.

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List of abbreviations

OV	Organic Variety
OHM	Organic Heterogeneous Material
PRM	Plant Reproductive Material
DUS	Distinctness, Uniformity, and Stability
KIS	Kmetijski Inštitut Slovenije - Agricultural Institute of Slovenia
RSR	Rete Semi Rurali
NGTs	New Genomic Techniques
VCU	Value for Cultivation and Use

Summary

The introduction of Organic Varieties (OV) and Organic Heterogeneous Material (OHM) as new cultivar types particularly suited for organic farming represents a significant scientific, agronomic, and regulatory advancement within the European organic sector. However, innovation at the breeding level does not automatically translate into economic viability. Our analysis confirms that label-based marketing is an effective instrument, as it supports price differentiation, facilitates premium market positioning, and increases market uptake, particularly when supported by coherent narrative frameworks and multi-channel communication strategies.

The objective of this study is to promote the uptake of organic breeding innovation by developing two marketing strategies as examples of how communication narratives and specific labelling can support increasing the market demand of organic products based on new cultivar types as well as the seeds of such cultivars. The methodological approach adopted for the analysis of the two cases is based on a qualitative mixed-method design combining case-study research, market analysis, and interviews.

The deliverable is structured in 5 Chapters: **Chapter 1** presents the background and objectives for the two cases, **Chapter 2** describes the analytical approach and case-study selection, **Chapter 3** reports on *Case study 1* (Organisation: Sun Agricoltura, Product: OHM-based pasta), **Chapter 4** reports on *Case study 2* (Organisation: Agricultural Institute of Slovenia KIS, Product: seeds of KIS beans varieties) and **Chapter 5** summarises the main constraints and key results across the two cases and general considerations on marketing strategies to promote organically bred cultivars. Across the two cases investigated, the most productive communication approach combines motivations such as digestibility, nutritional quality, and agronomic reliability, with motivations related to biodiversity, food sovereignty, and climate resilience. Hybrid communication tools, particularly QR codes linking physical packaging to digital content, are identified as a standard component of effective label implementation. Direct and experiential contact with end-users is identified as the most effective channel, with digital activity functioning as amplification rather than replacement of in person interaction.

The proposed strategies are designed to be replicable across diverse organic value-chain contexts and contribute to strengthening market demand for products derived from organically bred and diversity-based seed systems (PULL dimension of the LiveSeeding approach).

1. Background & objectives

This deliverable was developed in the framework of Work Package 6 (WP6) of the HORIZON Europe LiveSeeding project, Task 6.5, which aims to develop two pilot marketing strategies based on the narratives elaborated in T6.1 (D6.1, [Benefits of Organic Breeding](#)). The focus of T6.5 is the design of marketing strategies grounded in dedicated labels applied to final products derived from Organic Varieties (OV) and Organic Heterogeneous Material (OHM) (*Info Box 1*).

The LiveSeeding project is positioned within a transformative phase of the European organic sector. While organic farmland and market demand have grown steadily over the past decade, the seed systems underpinning this expansion remain structurally dependent on conventional breeding. A substantial proportion of organic farms continue to use cultivars derived from conventional breeding programmes. Addressing this structural gap is central to LiveSeeding's objectives. In this context, the development, recognition, and market integration of new cultivar types, namely Organic Varieties (OV) and Organic Heterogeneous Material (OHM), represent key innovation pathways. Both are embedded within the broader framework of organic seed systems and function as the systemic backbone linking breeding innovation, regulatory evolution, and market differentiation.

This deliverable aims to develop two pilot marketing strategies that focus on OV and OHM labels and serve as communication tools. It targets key actors in the organic breeding sector, including breeders, seed producers, farmers, food producers and retailers, while also addressing consumers as the ultimate drivers of demand.

The main objective is to promote the development of value-driven markets for products from organically bred cultivars. While these strategies support farmers and value chain actors in improving product differentiation and market positioning, they are ultimately designed to influence consumer perception and purchasing decisions, as end consumers play a central role in translating communicated values into actual market demand.

In doing so, the strategies strengthen demand and support the economic viability of organic breeding systems.

Current uptake of this breeding innovation shows that without structured marketing strategies the transformative potential of OV and OHM remains under-realised. With more effective communication, however, these innovations can contribute meaningfully to biodiversity, climate resilience, farmer autonomy, and value-driven consumer engagement within the European organic sector. In this context, marketing, particularly label-based marketing, is an essential mechanism for ensuring that OV and OHM fulfil their transformative potential within European organic value chains.

The specific **objective** of this deliverable is to support the uptake of organic breeding innovation via tailored marketing strategies that consider the peculiarities of integration and use of organically bred cultivars in the different links of the value chain, with specific focus on the end-users. These strategies also aim to communicate the added value of products derived from OV and OHM to consumers, thereby increasing awareness, acceptance, and their willingness to recognise and reward such value in the market.

Two pilot cases were selected to represent structurally distinct positions within the organic seed sector. The first case centres on **Sun Agricoltura**, a small agroecological farm in coastal Tuscany, Italy, producing pasta from a durum wheat OHM cultivar developed within the Rete Semi Rurali network. The second case centres on the **Agricultural Institute of Slovenia (KIS)**, a public research institution with a long-standing common bean breeding programme, developing a marketing strategy for the seeds of their varieties. For each case, the deliverable provides a pilot marketing strategy that includes an organisation overview, market research, competitive analysis, SWOT assessment, label implementation guidelines, marketing goals, customer segmentation, key messages, channel recommendations, and a phased activity matrix with measurable KPIs.

Info Box 1

Novel cultivar types defined in the EU Organic Regulation (2018/848):

Organic Variety suitable for organic production (**OV**) means a variety which is characterised by a high level of genetic and certain phenotypical diversity between individual reproductive units. For the production of organic varieties suitable for organic production, the organic breeding activities shall be conducted under organic conditions and shall focus on enhancement of genetic diversity, reliance on natural reproductive ability, as well as agronomic performance, disease resistance and adaptation to diverse local soil and climate conditions. All multiplication practices except meristem culture shall be carried out under certified organic management (Art. 3 (19), Annex II 1.8.4). Based on the implementing directives (EU 2022/1647 & 1648, there is a 7-year temporary derogation that allows easier registration of OV based on adjusted protocols for uniformity during the distinctiveness, uniformity, stability (DUS) test and ensures that the official multi-location trials to determine value for cultivation and use (VCU) are conducted under organic conditions.

FURTHER READING about OV:

Policy brief – Definition of Organic Plant Breeding for registration of Organic Varieties suitable for organic production

<https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/56308/>

Organic Heterogeneous Material (OHM) is a genetically and phenotypically highly diverse plant grouping within a single botanical taxon and produced in accordance with the EU Organic Regulation Art. 3 (18). It is therefore not considered a variety according to the definition of Article 5(2) of Council Regulation (EC) No 2100/94 and also not a mixture of varieties. OHM can be generated by multiple crosses of diverse parental material (composite cross populations, CCP) and/or on-farm management practices resulting in high genetic and phenotypic diversity. OHM is characterised by its dynamic nature to evolve and adapt to certain growing conditions and is intended to adapt to various biotic and abiotic stresses due to repeated natural and human selection and therefore is expected to change over time (EU 2021/1189). They can be commercialised without DUS and VCU testing after notification.

FURTHER READING about OHM:

Guidelines for OHM notification: <https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/56459/>

Training: What is organic heterogeneous material and how to notify it? <https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/56302/>

1.1 Market and consumer potential of new organic cultivar types

European consumers increasingly associate organic food with broader sustainability values, such as environmental protection, biodiversity conservation, and climate responsibility. Therefore, demand for organic products is driven not only by concerns about food safety, but also by ethical motivations and pro-environmental attitudes (Eyinade et al., 2021; Monier-Dilhan & Bergès, 2016). In this context, organically bred varieties (OVs) and organic heterogeneous materials (OHMs) provide opportunities for differentiation in sustainability-oriented markets. Biodiversity-related production attributes and locally adapted varieties can positively impact consumer perceptions of environmental value, especially when backed by transparent communication and product labeling (Böhm & Schäfer, 2025; Katt & Meixner, 2020).

However, the commercial relevance of breeding-related attributes depends on their visibility and comprehensibility at the point of purchase. Studies on food labeling show that consumers rely heavily on certification logos and simplified information when evaluating complex sustainability characteristics. Information provision can also influence consumers' willingness to pay for organic or environmentally friendly food products (McFadden & Huffman, 2017; Janssen & Hamm, 2011).

Although OV and OHM contribute to systemic benefits, such as climate resilience and genetic diversity, at the farm level, their market success depends on their perceived personal relevance to consumers. Organic purchasing decisions are usually influenced by health concerns, environmental awareness, trust in certification systems, and price-to-value perception (Jaramillo-Villanueva et al., 2025; Katt & Meixner, 2020).

Products derived from organically bred varieties or heterogeneous material are typically marketed under a general organic label, without clear differentiation from conventionally bred products, as organic agriculture is governed by process-oriented rather than product-based standards (European Parliament & Council of the European Union, 2018; Nuijten et al., 2017). These materials contribute to genetic diversity, local adaptation, and low-input performance, supporting biodiversity conservation and climate resilience (Wolfe et al., 2008; Nuijten et al., 2017). However, the dominance of conventionally bred varieties in organic systems obscures these benefits, limiting the recognition of their added value and reducing incentives for further innovation in organic plant breeding.

Marketing plays a crucial role in promoting the adoption of OV and OHM throughout the organic value chain. Marketing supports translating complex breeding processes into understandable product attributes, facilitates value recognition and price differentiation, and aligns breeding innovation with evolving market expectations (Katt & Meixner, 2020). Research on organic labelling and consumer behaviour shows that certification logos and simplified sustainability signals strongly influence purchasing decisions and willingness to pay for differentiated food products (Janssen & Hamm, 2011).

At the same time, OV and OHM face unique challenges in communicating with the market. Consumer awareness of breeding origin is limited, and technical concepts related to organic breeding or heterogeneous plant populations are difficult for non-specialist audiences to understand intuitively. Meanwhile, food markets widely use simplified marketing narratives referring to traditional or heritage varieties, which sometimes fail to reflect biodiversity-based breeding approaches. As organic products become more mainstream and price competition increases, it becomes both more difficult and more necessary to differentiate products credibly.

Therefore, structured marketing strategies are essential. These strategies should combine a clear visual identity with dedicated labels, accessible storytelling, evidence-based communication, and coordination across value chain actors (Messmer et al., 2021). In this context, marketing performs a promotional, facilitative, and educational function. By improving the visibility and recognition of OV- and OHM-based products, marketing strengthens the economic incentives for organic breeding and supports the long-term sustainability and competitiveness of organic value chains.

1.2 The role of label-based marketing

The translation of breeding innovation into market value requires effective communication instruments. Label-based marketing plays a critical role in bridging the gap between technical breeding processes and consumer understanding.

Dedicated labels linked to OV and OHM fulfil multiple strategic functions:

- ✦ **Trust and credibility:** Providing verified information about breeding origin beyond minimum legal compliance;
- ✦ **Recognisability:** Differentiating products derived from organically bred cultivars;
- ✦ **Narrative translation:** Communicating complex breeding concepts in accessible formats;
- ✦ **Value-driven purchasing:** Enabling end-users to align purchasing decisions with sustainability and biodiversity values (Janssen & Hamm, 2011; Katt & Meixner, 2020).

In this deliverable, labels are described not only as generic communication tools but are also integrated into the analysis of the two case studies and the development of the corresponding marketing strategies. In the Sun Agricoltura case, the OHM label is already operational and functions as a core element of product identity and communication, while in the KIS case, labels such as bioverita are considered as a prospective tool to strengthen product differentiation and market visibility.

The bioverita label (*see chapter 2.5*) provides a voluntary European quality mark for varieties originating from certified organic breeding, reinforcing transparency and market visibility. The OHM logo (*see chapter 2.5*) developed by Rete Semi Rurali (RSR) complements this approach by providing identity, traceability, and an open-source governance framework for heterogeneous populations.

Together, these labelling initiatives demonstrate how regulatory innovation (recognition of organic breeding and OHM) can be operationalised through market instruments that strengthen organic value chains.

2. Methodology and scope

The methodological approach adopted for the analysis presented in D6.4 was based on a qualitative mixed-method design combining case-study research, document review, market analysis, and structured interviews. The approach was conducted through several steps:

- **Case study selection** was conducted to identify relevant case studies representing different positions within the organic seed and food value chain.

The focus was on stakeholders using organic varieties and/or organic heterogeneous material, offering a final product or seed product with added value.

- **Market research** was an important step to understand the organic sectors in Italy and Slovenia. This involved the collection and analysis of data related to market trends, consumer habits, and sector development throughout the years
- **Review of relevant documentation and other literature**, including the review of company documentation, promotional materials, project outputs, and publicly available information.
- **Qualitative data collection** through structured interviews was conducted with selected case studies representatives to gather in-depth insights into product characteristics, market positioning, communication challenges, customer segment, and marketing goals in general.
- **Data analysis** was based on qualitative synthesis of the collected data, combining insights from interviews, market research, and document review. The analysis included the development of SWOT assessments, competition analysis, and identification of a unique value proposition for each case study. These analytical tools were used to structure the evaluation of market positioning, identify key constraints and opportunities, and inform the design of tailored marketing strategies.

The methodology approach described above formed the foundation for the analytical work presented in this deliverable. These steps directly support the objectives of D6.4 by translating analytical insights into practical strategies that strengthen product positioning, improve communication along the value chain, and support the uptake of organically bred cultivars.

The deliverable's scope is deliberately focused on marketing strategy: leveraging labels and storytelling to create value pull. It does not delve into detailed sales planning, pricing models, logistics, financial ROI, or in-depth breeding technicalities. Nor does it attempt a full quantification of OV/OHM markets or a comprehensive regulatory analysis beyond aspects directly affecting label implementation (e.g. packaging/label requirements in Reg. 2021/1189).

2.1 Case-study selection

A preliminary assessment was conducted in the context of a survey conducted with the LiveSeeding Living Labs to identify actors within the LL networks whose activities combined:

- ▣ Direct use of OV or OHM;
- ▣ A clearly identifiable final product;
- ▣ Existing or potential application of a dedicated label (OHM or bioverita);
- ▣ Market engagement beyond primary production;
- ▣ Willingness to participate in pilot marketing development.

Based on this preliminary assessment, two organisations were selected for deeper engagement:

- **Sun Agricoltura (Italy)**, representing an OHM-based cereal value chain with pasta as the final consumer product. This farm is part of the Rete Semi Rurali Resilient Cereals Living Lab in Tuscany.
- Agricultural Institute of Slovenia (Kmetijski Inštitut Slovenije – KIS), representing a prospective OV vegetable seed system with seeds of bean varieties as a product considered for this study. KIS is part of the Arable Crops Living Lab in Slovenia.

The selection ensures diversity in:

- ▣ Crop type (cereal vs. vegetable);
- ▣ Value-chain structure (processed food product vs. seed product);
- ▣ Organisational profile (small agroecological farm vs. public research institution);
- ▣ Market positioning (short local supply chain vs. institutional breeding programme).

Selecting two cases with different structures allowed to capture a wider range of challenges and opportunities related to the market uptake of organic varieties and organic heterogeneous material. This approach enables testing label-based marketing strategies in consumer and professional seed markets, improving relevance and transferability. It makes the two pilot marketing strategies stronger and supports their application in different organic value-chains.

2.2 Rationale for selecting the “Sun Agricoltura” case

Sun Agricoltura was selected as the OHM pilot case because the farm represents a fully integrated agroecological model in which Organic heterogeneous material of wheat, notified as OHM under the name Evoldur, is not only cultivated but also transformed into a final product - pasta. This vertical integration (seed → cultivation → processing → direct sale) allows for a comprehensive analysis of how the OHM label can function across the entire value chain.

Additionally, the farm demonstrates a strong and authentic link between biodiversity-based agriculture and market positioning. Its production model explicitly prioritises:

- ▣ Genetic diversity through wheat populations;
- ▣ Slow and controlled processing methods;
- ▣ Short food supply chains;
- ▣ Direct consumer engagement.

Sun Agricoltura also operates in a competitive premium pasta market, where differentiation based on biodiversity, digestibility, and agroecology is both relevant and necessary. The presence of organic certification combined with the OHM label

provides a unique opportunity to analyse how a specialised label can strengthen product identity beyond the general organic certification.

The farm's participation in LiveSeeding Living Lab with Rete Semi Rurali positions it within a broader innovation network, ensuring that the pilot strategy has transferability potential to other OHM actors. Finally, Sun Agricoltura is at a development stage where a marketing strategy can have a measurable impact. While structurally strong in production philosophy and product quality, the company faces challenges related to pricing, competition with industrial "ancient grain" narratives, and seasonal demand. This makes it a suitable case for testing label-based differentiation strategies.

2.3. Rationale for selecting the KIS Case

The Agricultural Institute of Slovenia (KIS) was selected as the OV pilot case due to its complementary institutional profile and its strategic relevance for organic seed systems.

Unlike Sun Agricoltura, KIS does not primarily operate as a food producer, but as a public research institution with a long-standing breeding programme. This creates a distinct value-chain configuration where the product is a seed (plant reproductive material) rather than processed food.

KIS was selected for the following reasons:

1. Strong institutional credibility and scientific foundation (over 120 years of activity)
2. Long-term bean breeding programme based on Slovenian germplasm;
3. Locally adapted, open-pollinated varieties with demonstrated organic suitability and a documented pathway toward OV certification
4. Clear alignment with climate resilience, organic suitability, and agroecological principles;
5. Identified need for improved market visibility and product differentiation.

KIS bean varieties (e.g., KIS Amand, KIS Marcelijan, KIS Pavlin) represent varieties adapted to Slovenian conditions developed with selection in organic conditions.

The Institute operates in a competitive seed market dominated by price-driven mass suppliers and imported brands. While KIS holds strong scientific credibility, its marketing and product visibility remain underdeveloped. This creates a strategic opportunity to analyse how a dedicated OV label (e.g., bioverita) could:

- Strengthen product differentiation;
- Translate breeding innovation into understandable market narratives;
- Reinforce local identity and trust;
- Support premium positioning based on adaptation and resilience.

2.4. Data collection and analytical approach

Following case selection, two structured in-depth interviews were conducted - one with the entrepreneur and farmer from Sun Agricoltura and one with KIS representatives. The main aim of the interview was to collect in-depth information and understand the organisation's strategy, product identity, label use, marketing approaches, and opportunities for new cultivar types of promotion. Each interview lasted around an hour and a half.

The interview was divided into 10 sections and included 42 questions (Annex 1).

The interview questions covered:

- Company overview – to understand the company's positioning, priorities within the organic food sector;
- Final product characteristics - to understand the unique qualities of the product that differentiate it in the market;
- SWOT analysis – to identify internal and external factors shaping strategic decision-making;
- Competition analysis – to analyse the competitors in the market;
- Unique Selling Proposition (USP) – to identify the core characteristic of the product that drives consumer preferences;
- Media presence – to assess current communication strategies, and to explore opportunities to enhance visibility;
- Customer segment – to define the target audience, and to explore new potential customers;
- Channels – to evaluate current channels in use, and explore new potential channels and communication tools;
- Marketing goals – to better understand and align company objectives with marketing activities;
- Use of labels – to better understand how certification and specialised labels can support marketing, differentiation, and customer trust.

In addition to interviews, supporting documentation was analysed, including:

- Brochures and promotional materials;
- Project-related communication outputs;
- Publicly available institutional information;
- Market benchmarking data where relevant.

The analytical approach combined qualitative synthesis of information provided in the interview with market analysis and communication channel discovery.

This analysis focused on understanding how label-based distinctions can translate breeding concepts into accessible narratives while building recognisable market identities, supporting value-based purchasing, and strengthening local value chains.

Figure 1 summarises the overall process of data collection, analysis, and marketing strategy development.

Figure 1 Overview of methodological approach applied in this study

2.5 Labels: bioverita standard and Rete Semi Rurali- OHM pledge

Dedicated labels such as bioverita and the RSR OHM logo represent pioneering instruments designed to increase the visibility of breeding origin within organic markets. Despite their shared purpose, the two labels reflect different approaches to certification, governance, and market identity, and understanding these differences is essential to appreciating how each function and in which context one should consider one over the other. The bioverita label is a European quality mark certifying plant varieties bred under organic conditions. Bioverita functions as a credibility and differentiation tool within organic markets. In contrast, the RSR OHM logo, developed by Rete Semi Rurali applies to genetically diverse populations and reflects a distinct approach based on heterogeneity, adaptability, and open-source principles. While both labels aim to increase the visibility of breeding origin, they differ in their underlying logic: bioverita is based on standardised certification of organically bred varieties, whereas the OHM logo represents population-based materials governed by open-source principles (Ajates et al., 2025).

In the context of this deliverable, these labels are considered complementary instruments for communicating breeding-related value. A more detailed comparison of their characteristics and applications is provided in the following section.

2.5.1 Bioverita association and its label

Bioverita was founded in Switzerland in 2011 as a non-profit association and has developed into a Europe-wide platform connecting organic and biodynamic breeders, seed producers, processors, traders, and other actors within the organic food sector (Bioverita, 2021). Bioverita certifies vegetable, cereal, fruit, ornamental, herb, and fodder varieties bred in organic conditions. Through its certification activities, the association supports breeding organisations that are committed to organic principles and strengthens the market position of organically bred varieties. In addition to certification, bioverita undertakes public relations work, participates in trade fairs and sector events, organises networking activities, and provides training and marketing support to its partners. Regular communication, newsletters, and visibility at professional events contribute to awareness-raising within the sector.

Figure 2 Vegetable with the bioverita label (Source: Bioverita)

The organisation does not directly finance breeding, sell seeds, conclude cultivation agreements, or provide direct agronomic advisory services. Instead, its role is to coordinate, mediate, inform, and accompany stakeholders in developing sustainable market structures for organic breeding. Successful cooperation with partner companies requires active engagement, including regular exchange, internal communication towards suppliers and customers, and joint promotion of the topic of organic breeding (Bioverita, 2021).

The **bioverita label** is a European quality label that promotes plant varieties and products derived from certified organic and biodynamic breeding (Figure 3).

Certification is based on strict criteria (own standard, yet in line with IFOAM guidelines and the Organic Regulation legal requirements) relating to the breeding process, following a two-stage evaluation procedure conducted by an independent label

Figure 3 bioverita quality label

seed packaging, product packaging, catalogues, assortment lists, invoices, and other promotional materials.

2.5.2 RSR OHM label

Figure 4 OHM label by Rete Semi Rurali in Italy

commission. The bioverita label serves as a voluntary quality mark for varieties originating from certified organic breeding. Recognition follows a two-stage evaluation procedure conducted by an independent label commission. The commission operates according to published criteria aligned with recognised principles of organic plant breeding. Only partners who are members of bioverita and who have concluded a user agreement are authorised to use the label. The label can be displayed on

The OHM logo (Figure 4) developed by Rete Semi Rurali (RSR) in Italy builds upon more than a decade of integrated work combining scientific research, on-farm experimentation, and policy engagement to promote diversity-based seed systems within organic agriculture.

Between 2010 and 2014, RSR activities focused on breeding strategies and the creation of genetic diversity. From 2014 to 2019, research addressed diversity dynamics and the functioning of seed systems. During the period 2017–2021, efforts concentrated on supporting an enabling

regulatory environment and expanding the number of crops involved. This phased approach ensured coherence between scientific evidence, farmer practice, and regulatory development.

The initiative evolved in parallel with European seed reform processes. Early reform attempts introduced temporary derogations allowing experimentation with heterogeneous material under organic regulation. Subsequent regulatory developments progressively recognised the legitimacy of Organic Heterogeneous Material as a distinct category, thereby creating space for marketing diversity-based materials outside the conventional variety registration framework. RSR played an active role in demonstrating the agronomic, economic, and social relevance of

composite cross populations (CCPs) and evolutionary populations within this evolving context (Ajates et al., 2025).

A key example is the SOLIBAM/FURAT bread wheat evolutionary population. The original population was created in 2009 at ICARDA in Syria. The material was subsequently introduced into Italy and cultivated continuously under organic conditions from 2010 to 2011 in two farms. Over time, it evolved into locally adapted populations, noted as SOLIBAM Florida in Tuscany and SOLIBAM Li Rosi in Sicily. These populations demonstrate dynamic adaptation through natural and farmer-led selection under organic conditions (Bocci et al., 2015). In this context, RSR has developed a dedicated logo for OHM and for products derived from OHM. The logo provides a clear and recognisable graphical identity that communicates the concept of diversity in an accessible manner. It includes key information such as the name of the notifier, the name of the OHM, the species, and the farmer producing the seed. This enhances transparency, traceability, and trust within the value chain.

A distinctive element of the OHM label is the incorporation of an open-source pledge (Ajates et al., 2025). Seeds marketed under this framework are not protected by plant variety rights. Instead, users are granted the freedom to resow, share, market, and further develop the material. In parallel, they accept specific obligations: not to apply intellectual property rights to the seeds or their derivatives, to maintain the same open-source pledge in subsequent dissemination, and to make further developments accessible to the original providers. This model promotes collective stewardship of genetic resources and prevents the privatisation of diversity-based materials. The OHM logo serves as both a marketing instrument and a governance tool, aligning breeding philosophy, legal principles, and market communication.

3. Results Case #1 Sun Agricoltura

3.1 Organisation overview

Sun Agricoltura is a young organic farm based on sustainable agricultural practices and alignment with natural ecological processes.

To provide a concise overview of the organisational and structural characteristics of the organisation, the key socio-economic features are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1 Socio-economic profile of Sun Agricoltura

INDICATOR	DESCRIPTION
Location	Costal Tuscany, Italy
Farm size	Approx. 8 ha
Established	2022
Management	Family-run
Main crops	OHM wheat (Evoldur), legumes, vegetables, olives
Production model	Organic, diversified, agroecological
Processing	Flour and pasta production
Value chain	Short supply chain, direct sales
Market channels	Farm outlets, bar, delicatessen-pizzeria, local tourism market
Partnerships	Rete Semi Rurali
Development stage	Early growth phase

Figure 5 Sun Agricoltura logo

The Sun Agricoltura farm (Figure 5) applies an integrated system in which soil management, crop production, and surrounding environmental conditions are treated as interconnected elements. The approach prioritises long-term soil quality, responsible use of natural resources, and farming practices that support ecosystem stability and sustainable productivity.

Overall, the farm is developing a production model based on organic practices, diversification, and local value chains. Its activities combine agricultural production, biodiversity conservation, and direct engagement with consumers through locally integrated commercial outlets.

Sun Agricoltura was established in 2022, when Claudia and Simone acquired previously abandoned agricultural land. At the time of purchase, the area was not operational and required significant restoration. The initial period focused on land rehabilitation activities, including clearing, basic infrastructure recovery, and

production planning. The development process was implemented gradually in order to allow environmental recovery and to align farming activities with the site's natural conditions and capacity.

Figure 6 Wheat fields at Sun Agricoltura (Source: Sun Agricoltura)

The farm is currently in an ongoing development phase and is managed by Claudia, Simone, and one employee. Operations continue to expand through improvements in infrastructure and a progressive increase in production diversity.

Sun Agricoltura is characterised by a strong link to agricultural research and the conservation of genetic diversity. This approach is influenced by the professional background of Claudia's father, Stefano Benedettelli, who worked for several decades as a crop variety researcher. His expertise has contributed to the farm's focus on heterogeneous wheat material (OHM) and the cultivation of the Evoldur wheat cultivar (Figure 6). As a result, the farm integrates production activities with the evaluation, reproduction, and preservation of plant genetic resources. Particular attention is given to the maintenance and reintroduction of traditional and ancient cultivars within contemporary local food systems. At Sun Agricoltura, biodiversity is addressed as a core operational objective. Farm diversification is a central component of its approach, both to support ecosystem functions and to improve the resilience of agricultural production. Crop rotation is applied as a key management practice, integrating cereals, legumes, vegetables, and green manure in order to enhance soil fertility and reduce reliance on external inputs. In addition to wheat production, the farm cultivates crops such as einkorn, chickpeas, and millet, and maintains an expanding vegetable garden. Fruit trees are also planted on an ongoing basis, contributing to the long-term development of productive areas and supporting overall ecological stability. This

gradual approach allows the farm to improve productivity and tree health while maintaining sustainable management practices and minimising stress on the plants.

Sun Agricoltura emphasizes agricultural production, product distribution, and market access.

Figure 7 RSR event at beach bar in Baratti Bay (source: Sun Agricoltura)

In order to support economic sustainability and maintain direct contact with consumers, the company operates two commercial activities linked to farm production: a bar located on the beach in Baratti Bay and a delicatessen–pizzeria in a nearby coastal town. These activities contribute to the development of a short supply chain, enabling direct use and sale of farm products and reducing intermediaries (Figure 7). This structure supports product traceability, strengthens the connection with local consumers and visitors, and promotes greater transparency in production and consumption. In 2023, Sun Agricoltura established cooperation with Rete Semi Rurali and became involved in collaborative European projects. This development increased the farm’s participation in innovation-oriented agricultural initiatives. Through these collaborations, the cultivation of Evoldur wheat became a key component of the farm’s flour and pasta production, supporting both economic activities and the farm’s focus on crop diversity. Although still in an early stage of development, Sun Agricoltura is implementing planned investments aimed at long-term growth. These include the renovation of an abandoned agricultural annex of approximately 100 m², intended to improve storage capacity and ensure compliance with hygienic and sanitary standards. In parallel, the farm continues to strengthen its logistical and operational infrastructure to support expansion.

3.2 Product Selected for the Marketing Strategy

A central product of Sun Agricoltura is pasta made from organic heterogeneous wheat material (OHM), primarily from the Evoldur cultivar (Figure 8). This material is notified to national authorities as EVOLDUR OHM and is labeled under the RSR OHM label. This product reflects the farm's production model, which prioritises agroecological

Figure 8 Sun Agricoltura pasta with OHM label (Source: Sun Agricoltura)

practices, local adaptation, and the use of genetically diverse plant material rather than standardised industrial varieties. Unlike conventional industrial wheat products, the raw material is derived from a dynamic population of seeds that is progressively selected. Selection criteria include nutritional quality, digestibility, and adaptability to local environmental conditions. The pasta, therefore, represents a direct output of the farm's cultivation system and its research-oriented approach to seed management. Evoldur plays a key role in determining both the agronomic and nutritional characteristics of the pasta. The cultivar is chosen not only for its yield but also for its nutritional profile. It is described as having lower gluten content and improved gluten digestibility and is considered suitable for consumers with non-celiac gluten intolerance, as supported by studies on ancient and diverse wheat types showing improved digestibility and reduced gastrointestinal discomfort (De Lorgeril et al., 2014; Sofi et al., 2014). It is also reported to have properties potentially beneficial for metabolic health, including glycaemic response (Dinu et al. 2018; Shewry & Hey, 2015). From an agronomic perspective, OHM materials such as Evoldur are characterised by gradual adaptation to local conditions, improved resistance to common wheat diseases, and higher flexibility under climate variability. These traits contribute to production stability and support long-term sustainability.

The processing method is designed to maintain product quality and preserve nutritional characteristics. The transformation process includes seed selection, controlled drying, wet stone milling, semolina production, extrusion, and slow drying. Pasta is produced using low-pressure extrusion and slowly dried at temperatures below 38 °C over a period of four to six days. This low-temperature drying process helps preserve product quality by reducing heat-induced damage and limiting the formation of furosine, a recognised marker of thermal processing and protein degradation in pasta (Giannetti et al., 2013; Hidalgo & Brandolini, 2018). The pasta is positioned as a product with high digestibility and nutritional value. The seed population is intentionally heterogeneous and selected over time for characteristics such as digestibility, nutritional performance, and antioxidant capacity. Studies on traditional and ancient wheat varieties indicate higher levels of bioactive compounds and antioxidant activity than in modern wheat, supporting these claims (Dinelli et al., 2011; Dinu et al., 2018). The product is described as free of furosine and is associated with reduced negative effects commonly reported for standard wheat-based products. According to the producer, it is reported that some medical professionals recommend the product for individuals in recovery phases or with sensitive digestion, due to its perceived lightness and digestibility.

Although the pasta is an important element of the farm's identity, it is not currently the main income source. The transformation process involves higher costs due to long drying periods and careful processing requirements, which increases the final consumer price and reduces short-term profitability. However, the pasta remains a strategic product for the farm, as it supports product differentiation, demonstrates the application of biodiversity-based agriculture, and links primary production with innovation and added-value processing. Organic certification and the OHM label contribute significantly to the product's credibility and market positioning. Organic certification aligns with the farm's overall production strategy, while the OHM label connects Sun Agricoltura to a broader network of farms cultivating similar wheat materials. This provides additional recognition and trust among consumers familiar with OHM and related seed systems. The pasta is presented as an agroecological product, directly linked to soil management, biodiversity conservation, and reduced dependency on external agricultural inputs. Its production model contributes to local food system development and supports food sovereignty objectives by promoting locally adapted cultivation and decentralised processing. The product addresses increasing consumer demand for wheat-based foods that are easier to digest and suitable for individuals with non-celiac gluten intolerance. Evidence suggests that products derived from diverse or ancient wheat populations may offer improved digestibility and potential health benefits compared to conventional wheat (De

Lorgeril et al., 2014; Sofi et al., 2014; Dinu et al., 2018). At the same time, the pasta is positioned as a high-quality staple product suitable for general consumption, rather than a niche dietary substitute. Over the next 12 to 24 months, Sun Agricoltura plans to strengthen the pasta value chain by upgrading laboratory and processing facilities to improve operational efficiency and economic sustainability. The company is also considering collaboration with nearby farmers to develop shared milling and pasta processing infrastructure, to reduce costs and expand local processing capacity.

In addition, the farm plans to expand educational and community-based activities, including bread-making laboratories for children and potential initiatives linked to school meal programs. These actions support the company's broader objective of promoting local food autonomy and demonstrating a replicable model of biodiversity-based agricultural production.

3.3 Market analysis

The market environment for Sun Agricoltura is shaped by sustained growth in the organic food sector in recent years. The growth affected evolving consumer preferences, the premiumization of cereal products, and tourism-driven food consumption.

Key statistical indicators of the Italian organic and pasta market

- Total Italian organic food sales exceeded 6.5 billion € in 2024, including 5.2 billion € in domestic consumption and approximately 1.3 € billion in out-of-home consumption channels (Nomisma, 2024).
- Exports of Italian organic products reached 3.9 billion €, representing a 7% increase compared to 2023, confirming the strong international positioning of Italian organic products (Nomisma, 2024).
- Organic agricultural land covered 2.51 million hectares (20.2% of total agricultural area), confirming Italy's leading position in Europe (FiBL & IFOAM, 2024; Eurostat, 2024).
- The number of organic operators has continued to grow, indicating ongoing structural expansion of the organic sector and strengthening market demand for certified organic production (FiBL & IFOAM, 2024)
- Premium pasta products are typically positioned in the upper price segment, with prices for differentiated products reaching several euros per 500 g depending on quality attributes (Bimbo et al., 2024).

- Coastal Tuscany remains a major tourism destination, with over 52 million overnight stays annually, supporting demand for local food experiences (IRPET, 2024)., supporting demand for local food experiences
- Tourism represents a significant driver of local food consumption in Italy, supporting demand for regional food products (ISTAT, 2024)

The continued growth of the organic food sector and consumers' increasing interest in authenticity, sustainability, and nutritional quality create favorable conditions for niche producers offering unique products. In this context, Sun Agricoltura's focus on biodiversity-based production and organic heterogeneous wheat is an asset. The premiumisation of the pasta market further supports this strategy. Rather than competing with large industrial producers on price, the farm can justify higher price levels through transparency, artisanal processing methods, and clear communication of added value. Using heterogeneous wheat material strengthens this differentiation by linking agronomic resilience with storytelling.

Tourism-driven food consumption provides an additional advantage. Direct-to-consumer channels, such as the beach bar and deli-pizzeria, enable experiential marketing, consumer education, and stronger customer relationship. However, reliance on seasonal tourism introduces revenue volatility and highlights the need for selective channel diversification. At the same time, competition from industrial brands that adopt simplified narratives may create consumer confusion and dilute the farm's perceived differentiation. This underscores the importance of structured communication strategies that translate complex concepts, such as organic heterogeneous material and biodiversity-based breeding, into accessible messages.

Overall, the most realistic growth pathway for Sun Agricoltura is to strengthen its niche position based on authenticity and quality. SWOT analysis of the organisation Sun Agricoltura operates in a context that offers strong potential but also demands constant adaptation. As a young farm still in a phase of reconstruction and growth, its strengths are deeply connected to its territory, its human capital, and its ability to combine agriculture with direct consumer interaction. At the same time, the organisation faces clear internal limitations linked to infrastructure, experience, and the seasonal nature of its market (Figure 9).

TECHNICAL	ECONOMIC	SOCIO	REGULATORY
<p>STRENGTH</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strong agronomic expertise and scientific support in decision-making Direct sales through own bar & pizzeria → short supply chain → higher trust & margins Diversified income sources Strong local identity & cultural value Direct relationship with consumers Alignment with agroecological principles 		<p>WEAKNESS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Incomplete infrastructure Fragmented land plots → logistical inefficiencies High initial restoration and renovation costs Seasonal income due to tourism dependence Dependence on external expertise Limited internal technical certification or formal agricultural credentials 	
<p>OPPORTUNITY</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Experimentation with new crops (e.g. barley) Innovation using ancient/traditional varieties Potential development of value-added products (e.g. craft beer) Growing demand for organic & transparent food systems Product diversification → new revenue streams Rising consumer awareness of food origin & quality Strong alignment with sustainability values Supportive policy trends toward organic and sustainable agriculture Access to innovation-oriented agroecological networks 		<p>THREAT</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited control over production costs Dependence on small-scale processing capacity Strong seasonality of tourism → unstable demand High production costs → higher product prices Price competition from large-scale producers Consumers sensitive to price over quality Weak regulation/clarity on labeling of “ancient wheat” products Limited protection against misleading market positioning 	

Figure 9 SWOT table for Sun Agricultura

Strengths

One of Sun Agricultura's most valuable strengths is its geographic position in the Baratti area. The area is both agriculturally favorable due to its climate and naturally attractive because of its landscape, cultural history, and tourism appeal. This provides the farm with a unique advantage: it is located in a place where people already want to visit, explore, and consume local products (Figure 10).

Figure 10 Location of Baratti region in Tuscany, Italy (Source: Wikipedia)

Another key strength is the strong technical and scientific support provided by Claudia's father, who acts as advisor and agronomist. His long experience in crop variety research gives the company access to high-level expertise that many small farms lack, strengthening both decision-making and the organisation's overall credibility.

Sun Agricultura is also reinforced by its commercial activities, which create direct contact with consumers. The bar and pizzeria serve as both sales channels and strategic spaces where the company can communicate its values, build relationships, and enhance

product visibility. This short supply chain provides an advantage in marketing and customer trust, as consumers can experience the farm's products directly in everyday contexts. Finally, the collaboration with Rete Semi Rurali and participation in projects such as [Resilienti](#) and SMAC strengthen the organisation through networking, knowledge exchange, and continuous learning. This connection gives Sun Agricoltura access to inspiration, collective identity, and shared experience, helping the farm develop beyond its own limited internal resources.

Weaknesses and internal challenges

Sun Agricoltura's internal challenges largely reflect the reality of starting from abandoned land. The farm was purchased in a completely neglected state, meaning that restoration has required long-term effort and continues to demand time, labour, and investment. Infrastructure remains another critical weakness. Important facilities such as the agricultural annex still require renovation, limiting the company's capacity to store and manage products efficiently. This creates additional pressure on logistics and reduces operational flexibility. The touristic nature of the region, while a strength in visibility, also creates internal limitations. Demand is highly seasonal, which makes income less stable throughout the year and complicates long-term planning. Logistical complexity is further increased by the fragmentation of land into separate plots, creating inefficiencies in transport and management. In addition, Claudia openly recognises that neither she nor her partner has formal agronomic training, meaning that a lack of structured agricultural education remains an ongoing internal challenge, even though it is partly compensated by external advice and experience-based learning.

Opportunities

Sun Agricoltura is well-positioned to benefit from broader societal trends. One of the most promising opportunities is the growing consumer awareness of organic food, nutritional quality, and transparent production systems. Increasingly, customers are interested not only in what they eat, but also in how food is grown and how it reaches the table. This cultural shift directly supports the company's values and strengthens the relevance of its short supply chain model.

The organisation also has clear opportunities for diversification. Since biodiversity is already central to its identity, expanding production into new crops aligns naturally with its long-term direction. Future experimentation with cereals such as barley, as well as potential development toward beer production using ancient varieties, could open new markets while maintaining coherence with the farm's ecological and innovative approach.

Threats

The external environment also creates risks that the organisation cannot fully control. The most serious threat is linked to the seasonal economy of the region. Because the area depends heavily on tourism, customer demand fluctuates significantly across the year, limiting consistent market stability and increasing vulnerability during low seasons.

Another major threat is product pricing. The high cost of production and transformation makes Sun Agricoltura's products more expensive, reducing accessibility for some local customers and creating barriers to expansion.

In addition, the organisation faces competitive pressure from large companies that market "ancient Italian wheat" products at lower prices. Although these products are not equivalent to Sun Agricoltura's OHM-based production, they can confuse consumers and create unfair competition, particularly when customers focus mainly on price rather than on production methods and authenticity.

3.3.1 Competition analysis

Sun Agricoltura operates in a market where competition is shaped less by direct local rivalry and more by differences in scale, pricing, and production philosophy. Rather than positioning itself against neighbouring farms, the company primarily sees the local agricultural environment as a space for collaboration. The focus is on building cooperative relationships and strengthening networks that support shared learning, biodiversity, and agroecological development. In this sense, local actors are viewed as potential partners in creating a stronger territorial food system rather than as direct competitors. The company identifies its main competitive pressure not at the small local level, but from large-scale producers. These actors dominate the market through lower production costs and cheaper final products, making it difficult for small farms with labour-intensive methods to compete on price. For Sun Agricoltura, the challenge is therefore not simply market presence, but the ability to maintain economic sustainability while preserving a high-quality and environmentally responsible production model. Sun Agricoltura's competitive advantage lies in the strong differentiation of its production and transformation process. The company emphasises a highly controlled approach, starting with careful seed selection and continuing through controlled pasta drying and storage. Transformation includes stone milling, low-pressure extrusion, and slow drying, all designed to protect nutritional quality and preserve the integrity of the raw material. This level of transparency and detail distinguishes the farm's pasta and flour products from industrial alternatives, where efficiency and speed often dominate processing decisions. The company's commitment to a short food supply chain strengthens this differentiation further,

ensuring traceability and a direct connection between cultivation, transformation, and consumption.

A defining element of Sun Agricoltura's market identity is its use of heterogeneous wheat material (OHM), particularly through cultivars developed and promoted within the Rete Semi Rurali framework. Participation in RSR projects not only strengthens technical development but also increases visibility and credibility, positioning the company within a recognised network of producers and research-based initiatives. This connection enhances the farm's reputation as an innovative, biodiversity-driven organization, providing products that are both artisanal and scientifically grounded, while being linked to broader agroecological movements.

3.3.2 Unique Selling Proposition (USP)

Sun Agricoltura's unique selling proposition is built on trust, transparency, and a production philosophy that connects biodiversity with human health. The company offers more than a final food product; it offers a complete and traceable process, carefully managed from seed selection to pasta on the plate. Customers are not only buying pasta, but also supporting an agricultural system based on respect for nature, independence from industrial supply chains, and the preservation of genetic diversity. A key element of this USP is the short and highly local food supply chain. The company maintains direct control over cultivation, processing, and final delivery, creating a strong relationship between producer and consumer. This closeness allows customers to see where their food comes from, to understand how it is made, and to build confidence through direct contact rather than marketing claims. Another major differentiating factor is the farm's deep connection to scientific research and long-term experience. The company's approach is strongly influenced by over 30 years of crop variety research carried out by the founder's father. This knowledge base strengthens the credibility of the product and supports the idea that Sun Agricoltura is not simply producing traditional food, but developing a modern, research-informed alternative to industrial wheat systems.

Sun Agricoltura responds particularly well to consumers who struggle with non-celiac gluten intolerance. Through the use of heterogeneous wheat material and cultivars selected for nutritional characteristics, the product is described as having low gluten quantity and high gluten digestibility, making it easier to tolerate for sensitive individuals. In addition, the pasta is considered potentially beneficial for diabetic individuals and is positioned as a clean, gentle, and nutritionally rich food. Its digestibility and safety make it attractive not only for health-conscious customers but also for people seeking food that supports recovery and overall well-being. Compared

to mass-market alternatives, the product offers a stronger focus on nutritional integrity and consumer health, supported by a controlled processing method. The USP is communicated primarily through direct interaction with customers. The company's pizzeria and other commercial activities serve as key spaces for personal conversations, storytelling, and building long-term relationships with consumers. These direct points of contact allow the company to explain its production values and create a stronger emotional connection to the product. Sun Agricoltura promotes its communication by utilizing social media platforms like Instagram and Facebook, as well as Google Business pages. Additionally, it seeks visibility through project-related platforms, including the Rete Semi Rurali networks. Together, these channels reinforce the message that the product is local, organic, and deeply connected to biodiversity, transparency, and quality driven by research.

3.3.3 Media presence

Sun Agricoltura maintains an active media presence that supports both its agricultural identity and its commercial activities. Communication is built around visibility, accessibility, and direct engagement with consumers, reflecting the company's broader emphasis on transparency and short supply chains.

Current platforms and visibility

The company is currently present on several key digital platforms, including Instagram, Facebook, Google business pages, and project- or network-related pages connected to broader initiatives and collaborations. These channels allow Sun Agricoltura to communicate its values, promote its products, and remain connected to both local customers and wider agroecological networks.

Best-performing channels

Among the existing platforms, Google and Instagram are identified as the most effective. Google plays a particularly important role through customer reviews and search visibility, especially when visitors and tourists actively look for food experiences, restaurants, or local products in the area. Instagram complements this visibility by providing a space for storytelling, showcasing products, and creating a recognisable identity connected to the farm's lifestyle and values.

Future communication development

To strengthen communication and improve overall organisation, Sun Agricoltura plans to develop a dedicated website. This is seen as an important step for better integrating the farm and its commercial activities under one clear structure, making it easier for customers to understand the full story of the company, access information, and connect with its products and services.

3.4 Implementation of the label in the organic value chain

Labels serve as the primary interface between production values and consumer perception in organic value chains. For Sun Agricoltura, the deployment of the Rete Semi Rurali (RSR) Organic Heterogeneous Material (OHM) label constitutes a central element of the marketing strategy. The label serves not only as a certification mark but also as a narrative that connects the product's agroecological identity to the expectations of informed consumers. In the case of pasta produced from the Evoldur cultivar, where the production process is complex and the underlying concept of OHM is not yet widely known to the general public, the label creates a visible and trustworthy shorthand for the values embedded in the product.

Sun Agricoltura currently operates with the RSR OHM label. on its products, linking it to the wider RSR network and to co-participating farms across Italy. In parallel, the company is involved in the development of a collective mark tentatively called the 'gentle pasta' label, developed together with a group of like-minded small-scale producers. This emerging initiative aims to establish a recognisable brand identity for pasta produced through an end-to-end agroecological process – from seed selection and cultivation of OHM material, through stone milling, to slow-dried extrusion. The development of this collective label is currently in progress and represents a significant strategic opportunity for the company within the next twelve to twenty-four months.

3.4.1 Connection of narrative with labels

The narratives established within the project provide a solid foundation for communicating the values behind OHM-derived products. Three narrative clusters are particularly relevant to the case of Sun Agricoltura and its pasta product:

1) **Local adaptation and climate resilience.**

The Evoldur cultivar is a heterogeneous wheat population that has been progressively selected to adapt to the specific soil and microclimate conditions of the Baratti coastal area of Tuscany. This dynamic adaptation process is directly reflected in the flavour, nutritional composition, and agronomic performance of each harvest. The RSR OHM label makes this locally embedded identity visible to consumers, aligning with the narrative that „for every land, the right seed; for every seed, the right land. “

2) **Community building and value chain collaboration.**

Sun Agricoltura's participation in the RSR network and in the Cereal Resilient Living Labs positions it within a visible community of breeders, farmers, and processors committed to the same production philosophy. The OHM label signals to consumers that the product behind it is not an isolated artisanal effort but part of

a verified, ethically grounded network. This narrative addresses altruistic consumer motivations related to supporting small-scale, collaborative food systems.

3) **Agrobiodiversity and food sovereignty.**

The pasta produced by Sun Agricoltura embodies the concept that food diversity begins with seed diversity. By using genetically diverse OHM material rather than uniform commercial varieties, the company contributes to the maintenance of cultivated biodiversity at the field level. The label provides the consumer-facing signal for this contribution, framing it within the broader narrative of independence from industrial seed systems and return to food sovereignty.

These narratives should be actively connected to the label through complementary communication tools. As demonstrated in D6.1, hybrid communication tools, particularly QR codes linking physical packaging to digital content, are highly effective in this context. In the case of Sun Agricoltura, the QR code on product packaging should direct consumers to a dedicated web page (to be developed as part of the company's website) that explains what OHM means, why Evoldur was chosen, and how the transformation process protects both nutritional value and seed integrity.

3.4.2 Guidelines for the implementation of the OHM RSR label

The following guidelines describe how the RSR OHM label should be implemented across Sun Agricoltura's product packaging, communication materials, and sales environments, in order to maximise its marketing impact while ensuring consistency with the RSR standards.

Product packaging

The RSR OHM label should be prominently displayed on the front of the packaging, next to the EU organic certification mark. Accompanying the label, there should be a brief explanatory sentence, such as: "Made with Evoldur, a living wheat population that adapts to its environment, bred for biodiversity." This sentence connects the label's visual identity with an explanation that is accessible to consumers.

Additionally, a QR code should be printed on the back or side of the packaging, directing customers to a dedicated landing page on the Sun Agricoltura website. This page should provide an explanation of OHM, a description of the Evoldur cultivar, a brief overview of the production process, and a link to the RSR network page for further information. Lastly, the name of the farm and its geographic location, Baratti, Tuscany, should be clearly stated on the packaging to strengthen the narrative of locality.

Point-of-sale environments

In the company's pizzeria, menu cards and table materials should reference the OHM label and include a brief note on what it means. A printed version of the core narrative ('this pasta is made from a living wheat population selected for your health and our land') should be visible at the counter or on the menu. Also, shelf cards or small printed information sheets should accompany any in-store product display. These should replicate the messaging from the packaging in a slightly expanded format, suitable for readers with more time and curiosity.

Digital channels

Instagram and Facebook posts featuring the product should always include a clear visual reference to the OHM label. Additionally, use consistent hashtags that align with the RSR network and the LiveSeeding project, such as #OHMwheat, #RetesSemiRurali, and #biodiversità. Photos on the Google Business profile must showcase products with the OHM label clearly visible to help visitors searching for artisanal or organic food in the Baratti area recognize the brand. Once the company website is developed, create a dedicated section titled "Our Seed Story" or something similar. This section should explain OHM, the Evoldur cultivar, and the RSR label, and include links to the broader RSR certification framework.

3.5 Marketing goal

3.5.1 Main goal

The main marketing goal for Sun Agricoltura over the next twelve to twenty-four months is to increase local brand awareness and consumer knowledge of its OHM pasta product, thereby generating a stable base of loyal, repeat customers in the Baratti and surrounding coastal Tuscany area. Given that the company is in an early stage of commercial development and that pasta from OHM material represents a premium niche product with higher production costs, the priority is not mass-market expansion but the consolidation of a defined, engaged local audience that understands and values the product's distinctive identity. This goal is fully aligned with the LiveSeeding PULL strategy: increasing and stabilising market demand for organic seeds and cultivars appropriate to organic farming. By building a local consumer base that actively seeks out OHM-derived products, Sun Agricoltura contributes to the economic sustainability of the broader organic heterogeneous material value chain.

3.5.2 Specific goal

The following specific goals operationalise the main marketing objective across a twelve- to twenty-four-month timeframe:

- 1) Develop and launch a company website within six months that connects the farm, the bar, and the pizzeria into a coherent online presence, includes a dedicated section explaining OHM and the Evoldur cultivar, and provides an e-commerce or direct enquiry function for the pasta product.
- 2) Increase the number of active followers on Instagram by 20% within twelve months through consistent posting of content that tells the story of the seed-to-pasta chain, highlights the nutritional benefits of Evoldur pasta, and promotes in-person events.
- 3) Establish at least two annual tasting or educational events (bread lab, field visit with degustation) that directly connect consumers with the OHM production narrative and introduce them to the pasta product.
- 4) Formalise the product offering within the pizzeria so that OHM pasta dishes are a permanent and clearly labelled item on the menu, with explanatory material available at the point of service.
- 5) Initiate at least one supply relationship with a local Horeca partner (restaurant, agritourism, or food retailer) within eighteen months, communicating the product's nutritional and agroecological attributes.

3.6 Customer segment

3.6.1 Primary customer segment

The primary customer segment for Sun Agricoltura's OHM pasta is the **health-conscious, quality-oriented** adult consumer resident in or regularly visiting the Baratti and coastal southern Tuscany area. Based on the interview with the company founder, the typical buyer is approximately forty years of age, lives locally or has settled in the region, and demonstrates a clear **preference for food quality over price**. This customer is not necessarily an expert in organic farming or seed systems, but is open-minded, curious, and willing to learn about what they eat.

The primary segment can be further characterised along two overlapping sub-profiles:

- 1) **Health-motivated consumers.** This sub-group includes individuals who are managing non-celiac gluten intolerance or who have received dietary guidance recommending easily digestible, nutritionally rich wheat products. This sub-group is motivated by direct personal benefit and is likely to become a loyal, high-value customer once the product's nutritional properties are clearly communicated.
- 2) **Conscious lifestyle consumers.** This sub-group is motivated by broader values of responsible food consumption, interest in local and short supply chains, and a preference for authentic, traceable products. They are already engaged with the organic food market and are receptive to narratives about biodiversity, small-scale farming, and the environmental significance of cultivar choice. They are likely to discover Sun Agricoltura through social media, Google search, or personal recommendation.

The primary segment is predominantly local and does not require a complex digital marketing infrastructure to reach effectively. It can be engaged most efficiently through direct in-person contact at the commercial activities (pizzeria, bar), through Google Business visibility, and through Instagram content that emphasises place, process, and taste.

3.6.2 Secondary customer segment

The secondary customer segment comprises visitors and tourists passing through the Baratti area, particularly during the summer season. The Baratti Gulf is an established tourist destination, attracting visitors interested in natural landscapes, coastal recreation, and authentic local food experiences. This segment is highly seasonal but represents a significant opportunity for direct product sales and brand exposure, particularly in the bar and pizzeria settings. Tourists typically encounter Sun Agricoltura through the bar on Baratti beach or through Google search when looking for local food experiences. They are receptive to the story of local artisanal production, especially when it is told in an accessible way at the point of consumption. However, given the nature of tourist flows, repeat purchasing is limited. The strategic value of this segment lies primarily in word-of-mouth amplification: a satisfied tourist who shares their experience on social media or recommends the product to others broadens the brand's reach at no additional cost.

A third emerging segment, currently in early development, consists of institutional buyers, including schools and public catering services. As referenced in the company interview, Sun Agricoltura is exploring a school lunch partnership with a local elementary school. Given the complexity of public procurement, this segment should be approached with a medium-term perspective.

3.7 Key messages – narratives

The key messages for Sun Agricoltura's marketing strategy are derived from the D6.1 communication framework and adapted to the specific context of the company and its product. Each message is formulated to address both egoistic-hedonic motivations (health, taste, personal experience) and altruistic motivations (environment, community, food sovereignty), in line with the evidence that combined approaches produce stronger consumer engagement.

The following messages (Figure 11) are proposed as illustrative examples of consumer-facing communication content, developed to demonstrate how the narrative clusters identified in T6.1 can be operationalised within Sun Agricoltura's specific market context.

Figure 11 Key messages for Sun Agricoltura connected with LiveSeeding Communication narratives (D6.1)

Message 1: From seed to pasta, every step matters (Narrative cluster: local adaptation and climate resilience)

“This pasta begins with a living wheat population. Seeds that are different from each other, selected over decades to be healthy, resilient, and deeply rooted in this land. We dry, mill, and shape them without heat or shortcuts. What reaches your plate is not just food, it is the result of care, science, and respect for nature.” This message directly communicates the production chain transparency and links the process to trust, which is the core of Sun Agricoltura's USP, as identified in the interview.

Message 2: Diversity in the field, diversity on your table (Narrative cluster: agrobiodiversity and food sovereignty)

“Our wheat does not look the same from plant to plant, and that is precisely the point. Genetic diversity makes it stronger, more adaptable, and more nutritious. When you choose this pasta, you support a way of farming that keeps seeds free, land alive, and food tasty.” This message speaks to the conscious lifestyle segment and addresses the altruistic motivations of biodiversity and food system independence. It is particularly suitable for Instagram and website content, where visual storytelling about field diversity and artisanal process can be combined with this textual narrative.

Message 3: This is Baratti wheat (Narrative cluster: local adaptation and climate resilience)

“The sea breeze, the clay soil, the Tuscan sun. Evoldur adapts to them year after year, becoming more of this place with every season. This pasta carries the flavour of where it was grown. It is not just organic, it is ours.” This hyper-local message addresses the motivational combination of taste and locality that, according to the D6.1 literature review, generates the highest consumer willingness to pay. It is most effective at the point of sale (menu cards, packaging, point-of-service cards) and in direct conversation with customers in commercial activities.

Message 4: Part of something bigger (*Narrative cluster: community building and value chain collaboration*)

“Sun Agricoltura is part of a network of farmers, researchers, and communities across Europe working to keep seeds free, farming diverse, and food honest. The OHM pinwheel on our packaging is a sign of this commitment, and an invitation to be part of the change.” This message connects the local product to the RSR network, providing social proof and embedding the product in a broader movement. It is most suitable for use in events, during guided tastings, and on the planned website.

3.8 Channels

The selection of marketing channels for Sun Agricoltura (Table 2) is guided by the company's current infrastructure, the characteristics of the target segments, and the need to maintain consistency between channel identity and product values. Based on the interview findings and the project's communication strategy framework, the recommended channel mix combines in-person, digital, and hybrid approaches.

Table 2 Sun Agricoltura media channels and description

Channel	Description
Pizzeria	Direct contact point with primary and secondary customer segments. Primary venue for tasting, storytelling, and product recommendation.
Bar	Seasonal touchpoint with the tourist segment. Strong opportunity for first product discovery and word-of-mouth during the summer.
Google Business profile	Currently identified as the most effective channel for customer acquisition. Should be maintained with up-to-date product photos, posts, and responses to reviews.
Instagram	Second most effective digital channel. Suited for visual storytelling of seed-to-pasta process, event promotion, and narrative content. Posting frequency: minimum 2-3 times per week.
Company website	Currently absent. Priority development within six months. Will serve as the hub for all channel links, product information, OHM explanation, online bookings, and e-commerce function.
QR code on packaging	Bridges the physical product with a digital narrative. Links to the OHM explanation page on the website. Recommended for all product packaging once the website is live.
RSR and LiveSeeding project channels	Provides access to a broader audience already familiar with OHM and organic breeding. Event announcements and product stories shared on RSR channels amplify reach beyond the local market.
Facebook	Lower organic reach than Instagram, but useful for community-based audience (purchasing groups, local associations). Secondary to Instagram for regular content.
Local media and press (traditional)	Currently not used. Could be explored once the website and events are established, particularly for the school lunch partnership.

3.9 Suggested activities

These activities are derived from the stakeholder interviews and analysis presented in previous sections and serve to operationalise the proposed marketing strategy into concrete actions. Activities are designed to be feasible for a small farm with limited resources and to progressively build brand visibility, consumer education, and product demand over twelve to twenty-four months.

Activity 1: Website development and OHM storytelling hub

Develop a dedicated website that integrates the farm, the bar, and the pizzeria into a single coherent digital identity. The website should include: a 'Seed Story' section explaining OHM and the Evoldur cultivar with accessible language and visual content, product pages for the pasta with nutritional and production information, a bookings section for events and commercial activities, and a map showing the location of the farm and commercial activities. The QR code on product packaging should link directly to the Seed Story page. This activity addresses the main marketing goal and supports all other channel activities.

Activity 2: Field visit and pasta tasting events

Organise two annual events that combine a guided visit to the wheat fields with an in-person tasting of pasta and bread made from Evoldur. These events should be held during spring and at harvest (early summer), leveraging the visual spectacle of a genetically diverse wheat population. Events should be promoted through Instagram, the website, and RSR channels at least three weeks in advance. During the events, printed materials explaining OHM and the RSR label should be distributed. A recipe card for home preparation of Evoldur pasta dishes should be offered as a take-home material. These events are the most powerful tool for first-person consumer conversion and word-of-mouth amplification.

Activity 3: Bread laboratory for children

Develop the planned collaboration with the local elementary school into a structured bread laboratory programme, in which children participate in the entire process from grain to bread. This activity serves multiple functions: it communicates the product's educational value to parents and the wider community; it generates local media interest; and it creates an emotional connection between the product and local family life. The bread lab should be documented through photos and short video content shared on Instagram and the website, with explicit parental consent.

Activity 4: In-venue product narrative integration

Integrate OHM pasta as a clearly described and permanently featured item on the menus. Menu descriptions should include a one-sentence explanation of the product's origin and characteristics. A small printed card or table insert should explain the OHM concept and the RSR pinwheel label to curious diners.

Activity 5: Consistent Instagram content

Establish a weekly Instagram content calendar with two to three posts per week, rotating between four content pillars: (1) Behind the process - photos and short videos from seeding, harvesting, milling, and pasta production; (2) Flavour and recipe - images of finished dishes with short recipe suggestions and taste descriptions; (3) The people and the land - photos of the farm team, the fields, the olive grove, and the Baratti landscape; and (4) Events and announcements - promotion of field visits, tastings, and collaborations. Stories and reels should be used to support reach. The OHM label and the RSR pinwheel should appear regularly in visual content to build recognition.

Activity 6: Horeca outreach

Identify two to three restaurants or agritourism in the Baratti and Livorno coastal area that position themselves as serving local, artisanal, or organic products. Approach them with a product presentation that includes: a tasting session, a product sheet with production and nutritional information, the RSR OHM label explanation, and a suggested wholesale price list. The communication approach should focus on the story value the product adds to their menu (local, traceable, unique wheat population) rather than on competing on price. A partnership with even one well-known Horeca actor in the region can significantly increase brand credibility and product awareness.

3.10 Matrix of activities

The matrix in [Table 3](#) presents the six proposed activities with their recommended timeline, primary channel, estimated resource intensity, responsible party, and suggested key performance indicators (KPIs). The activities are designed to be sequenced so that the foundational elements, the website, in-venue integration, and the Instagram programme, are established in the first six months, while more resource-intensive activities, such as the Horeca outreach, follow once the core communication infrastructure is in place. This phased approach allows Sun Agricoltura to build progressively without overstressing its current human and financial resources. Progress against the KPIs should be reviewed at six-month intervals. Given the informal nature of current marketing measurement at Sun Agricoltura, it is recommended that basic analytics tracking be established from the start of the implementation: website visitor data, Instagram Insights, and a simple monthly log of Horeca enquiries and event attendance. This lightweight monitoring system will enable evidence-based adjustment of the strategy over time and will provide data for future reporting.

Table 3 Matrix of activities for Sun Agricoltura

Activity	Timeline	Primary Channel	Responsible	Suggested KPIs
1. Website development and OHM hub	Months 1-6	Digital (website)	Sun Agricoltura + web developer	Website live; Seed Story page views; QR code scans per month
2. Field visit & tasting events	Twice/year (e.g. April & June)	In-person + Instagram + RSR channels	Sun Agricoltura + RSR	Number of participants per event; post-event social media reach; new product customers acquired
3. Bread laboratory for children	Months 4-8 (school year)	In-person + Instagram	Sun Agricoltura + school	Number of sessions; children/parents reached; media mentions; Instagram engagement on related posts
4. In-venue product narrative integration	Month 1 onwards	In-person (pizzeria, bar)	Sun Agricoltura	Customer questions/comments on product story; customer feedback on menu description; repeat visits by health-motivated customers
5. Instagram content programme	Ongoing from Month 1	Instagram + Facebook	Sun Agricoltura	Follower growth (+20% in 12 months); engagement rate; reach per post; profile visits; website link clicks
6. Horeca outreach	Months 6-18	In-person + digital (product sheet)	Sun Agricoltura	Number of partner restaurants; volume of product sold through Horeca channel; menu placements featuring Evoldur pasta

4. Results Case #2 KIS

4.1 Company overview

The Agricultural Institute of Slovenia (Kmetijski inštitut Slovenije – KIS) is one of Slovenia’s leading institutions in the field of agricultural research, development, and professional support. With more than 120 years of continuous activity, the Institute has played an important role in the modernisation and improvement of Slovenian agriculture (Figure 12).

Figure 12 Location of Ljubljana region (Source: Matjaž Glavan, researchgate)

To provide a concise overview of the organisation and socio-economic characteristics of the case-study organisation, the key features of KIS are summarised in Table 4.

Table 4 Organisational profile of the Agricultural Institute of Slovenia (KIS)

INDICATOR	DESCRIPTION
Location	Slovenia
Farm size	Not applicable (research institute)
Established	120+ years
Management	Public research organisation
Main work-fields	Research, plant breeding, laboratory analysis, advisory services
Key expertise areas	Crop science, genetics, plant breeding, soil monitoring
Main crops	Bean varieties, and other
Production model	Research-based plant breeding and variety development
Processing	Not applicable
Value chain	Breeding and seed development
Market channels	Seed distribution through partners and agricultural networks
Partnerships	National and international research networks
Development stage	Established institution with continuous innovation activities

Figure 13 Researchers at KIS (source: KIS)

Over time, KIS has maintained its relevance by adapting its research priorities and services to changing environmental, economic, and policy conditions.

The Institute operates to support the long-term development of the agricultural sector, with a focus on productivity, sustainability, food security, and the responsible use of natural resources. Its work contributes to the improvement of agricultural production systems and the competitiveness of Slovenian agriculture, while also addressing broader environmental and societal needs.

KIS is structured as a multidisciplinary organisation with expertise across a wide range of agricultural and related scientific fields. Its core areas include crop science, genetics, plant breeding (Figure 13), conservation of plant genetic resources through gene bank activities, plant protection, soil monitoring and quality assessment, agricultural ecology, agricultural engineering, renewable energy applications in agriculture, and agricultural economics. This broad competence allows the Institute to address agricultural challenges through integrated approaches that consider biological, technical, and socio-economic aspects.

The Institute conducts basic, applied, and developmental research and supports the transfer of scientific knowledge into practical use. Research activities are complemented by advisory and expert services aimed at farmers, agricultural stakeholders, public institutions, and industry. In addition, KIS provides laboratory analyses, monitoring programs, and professional support services that contribute to evidence-based decision-making in the agricultural sector.

Quality assurance and reliability are key elements of the Institute's operational framework. KIS has established certification procedures and standardised methods for testing and evaluation, particularly in areas related to food quality, authenticity, and agricultural inputs. These activities strengthen trust in the Institute's outputs and ensure that results are consistent and usable for both national and international partners.

Figure 14 Dissemination event of breeding activities at KIS (source KIS)

A significant part of the Institute's contribution is linked to plant breeding and variety development (Figure 14). Through long-term breeding programs, KIS has developed and registered Slovenian crop varieties adapted to local growing conditions and resilient to environmental stress factors. These varieties provide practical benefits for farmers by improving yield stability and production efficiency, and they also contribute to national agricultural resilience by supporting domestic breeding capacity. Certain breeding efforts also take into account the needs of organic farming systems and low-input agricultural practices.

KIS actively responds to current and emerging challenges such as climate change, biodiversity loss, sustainable management of soil and water resources, and increasing consumer demand for safe and high-quality food. The Institute supports research and development aimed at reducing environmental impacts, improving resource efficiency, and strengthening the sustainability of agricultural systems.

In addition to research and services, KIS plays an important role in education, training, and capacity building. It contributes to the development of highly qualified experts, supports postgraduate research activities, and cooperates with universities and research institutions. The Institute also collaborates with agricultural organisations, private sector stakeholders, and international partners, strengthening its position within the European research environment and enabling participation in joint projects and innovation networks.

Today, KIS represents a central institution for agricultural research and development in Slovenia. Through its scientific work, technical services, and cooperation with stakeholders, it contributes to innovation, supports sustainable agricultural practices, and strengthens the overall resilience and competitiveness of the national food and agricultural system.

4.2 Key products

At the centre of the Agricultural Institute of Slovenia's (KIS) market-oriented activities is the development and supply of seed material, particularly Slovenian common bean varieties and Organic Heterogeneous Materials (OHM). These products are developed through the Common Bean Breeding Programme and represent a direct application of long-term scientific research into practical planting material for farmers, small producers, and gardeners. KIS bean varieties are designed as breeding outputs that support future food production by providing improved cultivars adapted to Slovenian environmental conditions. The programme focuses on increasing yield stability, improving resistance to biotic and abiotic stress, and supporting sustainable production systems. In this context, KIS does not primarily offer processed food products, but agricultural inputs that influence long-term production capacity and resilience. A major advantage of the programme is Slovenia's diverse common bean germplasm. The genetic variability developed through long-term local cultivation provides a strong foundation for breeding activities. KIS uses this germplasm as a base for systematic breeding and selection, resulting in new varieties that combine locally adapted traits with improved performance under current agricultural challenges, including climate variability, disease pressure, and changing production demands. The breeding programme includes both climbing and dwarf bean types, developed for different uses such as fresh pod consumption, dry bean production, or combined applications. This ensures relevance for a wide range of end users, including professional growers, small farms, and hobby gardeners. Among the key outputs of the programme are new Slovenian bean varieties such as KIS Amand, KIS Marcelijan, and KIS Pavlin (Figure 15, Figure 16). These varieties have been developed with defined agronomic and quality-related objectives. Depending on the cultivar, breeding goals include early maturation to reduce exposure to high summer temperatures, improved tolerance to less favourable climatic conditions, stable yield performance, and enhanced culinary traits such as pod quality and reduced string formation. Nutritional

value is also considered an important selection criterion, with several varieties reported to contain increased levels of proteins, minerals, and trace elements compared to other European genetic sources.

Figure 15 KIS Pavlin (Source: KIS)

In addition to conventional varieties, KIS has introduced Organic Heterogeneous Materials (OHM) as an innovative product category. OHM products differ from standard varieties because they intentionally contain genetic diversity within a population rather than uniform characteristics. This diversity increases adaptability to variable field conditions and supports production systems where environmental stress, pests, and disease pressure cannot be fully controlled.

Two major OHM products developed by KIS are KIS Bogo and KIS Deodat. These materials demonstrate variability in specific traits, such as pod characteristics, flower colour, seed coat patterns, and resistance to diseases such as bean anthracnose (*Colletotrichum lindemuthianum*). This heterogeneity contributes to greater resilience at the population level, ensuring that overall production remains stable even if individual plants are affected by stress factors. These characteristics are particularly relevant for organic farming systems, where chemical plant protection is limited. The development of both pure line varieties and OHM products reflects a breeding strategy aligned with sustainable and agroecological principles. KIS breeding priorities include tolerance to heat and water deficiency, resistance to common diseases and viruses, and suitability for organic cultivation. These traits address key risks linked to climate change and support the development of more resilient cropping systems. The products provide value across multiple stakeholder groups. Farmers benefit from access to locally adapted cultivars that reduce production risks and improve yield stability. Organic producers gain planting material that supports resilience without dependency on synthetic inputs. Gardeners benefit from reliable and high-quality

varieties suitable for traditional cultivation. Consumers benefit indirectly through improved product quality, nutritional value, and support for local food systems.

Figure 16 KIS Marcelijan (Source: KIS)

In the next phase of development, KIS does not prioritize large-scale industrial expansion, as seed multiplication is constrained by available land and labour requirements. Instead, the strategic focus for the next 12 to 24 months is on strengthening market presence, improving product visibility, and increasing recognition of these varieties as Slovenian-developed breeding outputs that combine national genetic heritage with modern agricultural research and sustainability objectives.

4.3 Market research

The market environment for the bean seeds bred by the Kmetijski inštitut Slovenije – KIS is shaped by a relatively limited scale of organic vegetable production, the growing importance of organic food systems, and the strong cultural relevance of hobby gardening. These important factors influence both demand and competitive positioning opportunities for science-based seed suppliers.

Empirical market context for the Slovenian seed and organic farming sector

- Organic farming has continued to expand in Slovenia. In 2024, the organic system included 3,968 agricultural holdings cultivating around 56,800 hectares, representing an increase compared to the previous year and confirming the structural relevance of the organic production system (Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia, 2025)
- Long-term trends show strong growth of organic agriculture. The area under organic farming increased from **approximately 2,400 hectares in 1999 to more than 54,600 hectares by 2023**, reflecting favourable policy support and market opportunities (Slovenian Environment Agency, 2025).
- Organic land use in Slovenia is structurally dominated by extensive production systems. **Permanent grassland accounts for about 78–79% of organically**

managed land, indicating a strong link between organic farming and low-input livestock systems (European Environment Agency, 2025).

- Slovenian agriculture is characterised by relatively small farms. National rural development documentation reports **around 69,900 agricultural holdings with an average farm size of about 6.8 hectares**, limiting economies of scale and influencing demand for locally adapted inputs (European Commission, 2025)
- Organic farming in Slovenia represents approximately **11% of utilised agricultural area**, placing the country slightly above the EU average and confirming the growing strategic importance of organic production (Willer et al., 2024).

These structural characteristics suggest that the Slovenian seed market provides few opportunities for large-scale commercial growth in crop-specific sectors, such as beans. The predominance of small farms and extensive production systems limits the economic feasibility of volume-driven seed multiplication strategies. Conversely, the continued growth of organic farming emphasises the importance of breeding methods that focus on locally adapted genetics, resilience, and consistent performance under low-input conditions. Organic production systems rely more heavily on genetic diversity and adaptive traits, creating favorable conditions for innovation in organic heterogeneous material. The structural dominance of smallholder agriculture implies that trust, advisory services, and knowledge transfer play central roles in adoption decisions. This creates opportunities for research institutions, such as KIS, to differentiate themselves through not only seed products but also integrated support services, including demonstration trials and technical guidance.

Overall, KIS's most realistic strategic positioning lies in developing a specialist identity based on scientific credibility, local adaptation, and targeted market visibility rather than competing with industrial seed suppliers on price or production scale.

4.3.1 SWOT analysis of the organisation

The position of the Agricultural Institute of Slovenia (KIS) in the seed and breeding market is unique. Unlike commercial seed companies whose primary goal is volume and profit, KIS operates from a different starting point: science, national responsibility, and long-term sustainability. This difference shapes both its competitive advantages and the challenges it faces when entering a market dominated by large international producers (Figure 17).

TECHNICAL	ECONOMIC	SOCIO	REGULATORY
<p>STRENGTH</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strong in-house R&D (researchers, labs, field trials) Ability to respond to climate & disease challenges Locally adapted breeding programmes (Slovenian germplasm) Competitive advantage through innovation capacity Reduced dependence on external R&D partners High institutional credibility & trust among farmers Strong national identity & heritage value Operates under certified and internationally recognised standards Integration within national agricultural research frameworks 		<p>WEAKNESS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Infrastructure not optimised for mass production Labour-intensive bean harvesting (manual work) Limited production volume → restricted market expansion High seasonal labour costs Organisational focus divided across multiple research priorities Difficulty attracting seasonal field workers Research mandate limits full commercial orientation Not structured as a market-driven seed company 	
<p>OPPORTUNITY</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demand for climate-resilient, locally adapted varieties Development of nutritionally enhanced beans (protein, minerals) Expansion of organic heterogeneous materials (e.g. KIS Bogo, KIS Deodat) Growth of hobby gardening & home food production market Premium positioning through differentiation (quality over volume) Rising consumer preference for local & sustainable seeds Increased awareness of resilience & biodiversity Expansion of the organic farming sector Policy support for agroecology & genetic diversity 		<p>THREAT</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Climate instability (droughts, heatwaves, storms) → yield risk High sensitivity to bad production seasons Strong price competition from large international seed companies Risk of market shift toward cheaper imported seeds Consumers prioritising price over origin & quality Need for strong branding & education to communicate value Exposure to international market liberalisation Limited structural protection for small national breeding programmes 	

Figure 17 SWOT table for KIS

Strengths

KIS's greatest strength is its scientific foundation. The Institute is not dependent on external R&D partners; it holds deep in-house expertise, researchers, laboratories, and experimental infrastructure that allow it to develop, test, and validate new plant varieties based on real agricultural needs. This gives KIS the ability to respond to emerging threats such as climate change, disease outbreaks, and shifting production demands with a level of credibility and precision that many commercial competitors cannot easily match. Its long tradition further strengthens this advantage. With more than 120 years of continuous presence in Slovenian agriculture, KIS carries a reputation that is difficult to replicate. It is not just seen as another market player, but as a trusted national institution. This credibility creates an important emotional and professional trust among growers, farmers, and stakeholders who value reliability, local expertise, and Slovenian agricultural heritage. Another major strength lies in quality assurance and professional systems. KIS operates within strict standards, supported by accredited laboratories and internationally recognised certifications. This ability to control quality and ensure scientific reliability strengthens confidence in its seed products, especially when the product is positioned as something more than just "another bean seed," but rather as a locally developed and validated solution. Finally, the bean breeding programme itself represents a strong competitive asset. It is built on centuries of Slovenian germplasm and supported through national funding and research frameworks. This gives KIS a strategic advantage in developing varieties

that are genuinely adapted to Slovenian conditions, varieties that are not imported and adjusted later but created with Slovenia as the starting point.

Weaknesses

Despite its strong scientific position, KIS faces internal limitations that make commercial expansion challenging. The most significant is production capacity. The Institute is not a seed company focused on one crop; it is a broad research institution with many priorities. This naturally limits the land, infrastructure, and operational focus available for large-scale seed multiplication. As a result, KIS cannot easily respond to high market demand with mass production volumes. Labour availability is a significant weakness, particularly because bean harvesting relies heavily on manual labor. It has become increasingly challenging to find enough workers willing to engage in physically demanding seasonal work, especially under high summer temperatures. This shortage not only limits production capacity but also places greater operational pressure on the program. KIS also faces challenges in sales logistics and distribution. While the Institute has the product, the market requires a system: retail availability, clear purchasing channels, and consistent access for end customers. Without strong distribution partnerships, even high-quality varieties risk remaining niche. Online sales could be a solution, but the economics are uncertain; delivery costs can easily outweigh the low price of small seed packages, creating barriers for profitability.

Opportunities

The market environment is shifting in ways that strongly favour KIS's product philosophy. One of the most promising opportunities lies in the growing popularity of hobby gardening and small-scale home food production. Slovenia has a strong tradition of home gardening, and this segment represents a natural customer base for bean varieties, especially when they are positioned as locally developed and Slovenian-grown.

Another opportunity is the rising demand for locally adapted varieties. Climate instability is pushing growers to search for cultivars that can handle drought, heat stress, and unpredictable seasons. This is exactly where KIS has a strong story: varieties developed from Slovenian germplasm, tested in Slovenian conditions, and bred specifically for resilience.

KIS also has the opportunity to grow through differentiation rather than scale. Nutritional improvements in bean varieties, such as higher protein content or increased trace minerals, create a strong platform for storytelling and premium positioning. While KIS does not produce food products directly, these traits open

doors for collaboration with local food producers, organic brands, and speciality retailers looking for high-value raw materials.

The growth of organic farming is another strong opportunity. Organic heterogeneous materials such as KIS Bogo and KIS Deodat are perfectly aligned with modern agroecological trends, where genetic diversity and resilience are becoming a competitive advantage. As demand increases for sustainable and chemical-free inputs, KIS is already positioned in a category that feels future-oriented and innovative.

Threats

The largest external threat remains the same factor that affects all agricultural production: weather and climate uncertainty. Seed production depends heavily on stable seasons, and unpredictable droughts, storms, or heatwaves can directly reduce yields and quality. For a programme with limited production capacity, even one bad season can significantly affect market availability. Competitive pressure is also strong. Large international seed producers, especially from neighbouring countries such as Italy, operate with far greater economies of scale. They can produce massive quantities at lower prices, making price-based competition nearly impossible for KIS. This creates a market reality where KIS must win through differentiation, trust, and storytelling rather than cost. In addition, labour shortages and rising labour costs represent a growing threat. Even if demand increases, KIS may struggle to scale production without reliable seasonal workforce availability. This can widen the gap between market potential and operational capacity.

Finally, there is the ongoing risk of market behaviour shifting toward cheaper imported seeds. If consumers prioritise price over origin and quality, local Slovenian varieties could struggle for shelf space unless their value is clearly communicated. For KIS, this means that branding, education, and positioning are not optional; they are essential for long-term competitiveness.

4.3.2 Competition analysis

The competitive landscape in the Slovenian bean seed market is shaped by a clear imbalance: on one side stand large commercial seed producers with strong production power and distribution reach, and on the other side stands KIS, a research-driven institution offering a highly specialised product rooted in Slovenian agricultural heritage. This makes the market less of a traditional “brand vs brand” competition, and more of a strategic battle between scale and differentiation. At the local and regional level, the strongest direct competitors are large seed companies, most notably those originating from Northern Italy. These producers supply Central European markets with large volumes of bean seed and have built strong distribution

channels that naturally extend into Slovenia. Their presence is felt most strongly through availability; these seeds are already established in garden centres, agricultural stores, and retail networks, making them an easy default choice for many buyers. In addition to these large foreign suppliers, smaller regional competitors also exist, although they appear less dominant. These tend to focus more on ecological seed production and niche segments, serving customers who actively seek organic or sustainability-oriented alternatives. While their scale is smaller, they compete more directly with KIS in terms of values and positioning, especially among environmentally conscious consumers. When it comes to positioning, Italian competitors dominate primarily through price. Their economies of scale allow them to offer lower-cost seed packages and a stable supply, giving them a strong advantage in a market where many customers still purchase seeds based on convenience and affordability rather than origin or breeding background. Their branding, however, tends to follow a standard commercial approach, functional packaging, generic messaging, and little emotional connection to the customer. In many cases, their value is not built on a unique identity, but on being “good enough” and always available. Quality among these competitors can vary. Seed age, storage conditions, and supply chain management all influence germination and performance, meaning that the competitive edge does not always come from superior product quality, but from market dominance and distribution power. KIS enters this market from a fundamentally different position. It cannot compete on volume or price, but it does not need to. Its competitive strength lies in offering something competitors cannot easily replicate: scientifically developed Slovenian varieties created specifically for Slovenian conditions. While large foreign producers develop cultivars for broad markets, KIS varieties are shaped by Slovenian climate realities, Slovenian soil conditions, and Slovenian consumer preferences. This gives KIS a natural advantage in relevance and adaptation, especially as weather patterns become more unpredictable and growers increasingly value reliability over cheap input costs.

The Institute also differentiates itself through the depth of its product development story. These seeds are not generic commercial varieties; they are the result of structured breeding programmes built on Slovenian germplasm developed over centuries. This connection to national agricultural heritage creates a strong foundation for positioning, especially among customers who care about local origin, tradition, and long-term food security. Another important differentiator is the presence of organic heterogeneous materials (OHM) such as KIS Bogo and KIS Deodat. This is where KIS moves beyond “local” and into “innovative.” OHM varieties are intentionally diverse, meaning they contain genetic variability that supports resilience in real-life farming conditions. This feature becomes increasingly valuable in organic

agriculture, where growers have limited access to chemical plant protection tools and rely more on natural adaptability. Compared to uniform industrial cultivars offered by many competitors, OHM products position KIS as a forward-thinking player aligned with agroecology, biodiversity, and climate resilience. In practical terms, KIS offers customers a solution that is better adapted to the challenges they face: heat stress, water deficiency, and disease pressure. Its varieties are developed with functional advantages, resistance to common diseases and viruses, stable yields even in less favourable seasons, and improved culinary qualities such as stringless pods or desirable texture. Some varieties also offer enhanced nutritional profiles, including higher protein content and valuable trace elements, which opens additional potential for premium positioning. This means KIS does not solve the same customer problem as large foreign seed companies. Competitors mainly solve the problem of easy access and low-cost seed supply. KIS solves a deeper problem: the lack of locally adapted, resilient bean varieties that can perform reliably under Slovenian growing conditions while also supporting sustainable and organic farming practices.

Ultimately, the competitive advantage of KIS is built on trust, scientific credibility, and national relevance. Customers who choose KIS are not only buying a packet of seeds, but they are also investing in Slovenian agricultural knowledge, biodiversity, and the future of local food production.

4.3.3 Unique Selling Proposition (USP)

In the bean seed market, it is easy for products to start looking the same. On the shelves, many varieties come in similar packaging, carry similar promises, and are often priced to compete in a race toward the cheapest option. Large foreign seed producers, especially those supplying Central Europe from Northern Italy, have built their position exactly on this advantage: scale, availability, and low price. KIS enters this market from a completely different place. It does not compete as a mass producer, and it does not try to win by offering the lowest-cost seed. Instead, its strength lies in something far more valuable and much harder to replicate: its seeds are the result of Slovenian science, Slovenian agricultural heritage, and breeding work developed specifically for Slovenian growing conditions. The bean varieties created through the Common Bean Breeding Programme are not generic cultivars designed for broad European markets. They are built from Slovenian germplasm that has been shaped by centuries of cultivation and consumer preference. KIS takes this genetic heritage and upgrades it through modern research, transforming tradition into innovation. Every variety carries a clear purpose: better resistance to disease, improved tolerance to heat and water stress, stronger yields under unstable weather conditions, and improved nutritional or culinary traits.

This is where the real uniqueness of KIS lies: it is not selling “just seed,” but offering growers and gardeners a locally adapted tool for reliable production. In a time when climate change is no longer a future scenario but a real threat, the ability to plant varieties bred for resilience becomes a competitive advantage. KIS varieties offer stability where other products offer only standardisation.

The strongest expression of this uniqueness can be found in KIS’s organic heterogeneous materials. Ultimately, the USP of KIS bean varieties is built on one simple truth: these are Slovenian-developed seeds created with a scientific purpose. They are designed to perform in Slovenia, for Slovenian growers, in Slovenian conditions, offering not only better adaptation and quality, but also a stronger connection to local agriculture, biodiversity, and the future of sustainable food production.

4.3.4 Media presence

KIS currently maintains a limited but structured media presence, primarily based on two communication channels: its official website and its Instagram profile. Although the Institute carries out a wide range of research and professional activities, its external communication remains focused mainly on providing institutional information and ensuring transparency, rather than on active product promotion or broader public visibility.

The official website represents the main communication platform of KIS. It provides comprehensive information on the Institute’s mission, organisational structure, research areas, projects, and professional services. The website also plays an important role in establishing institutional credibility, particularly for stakeholders such as public authorities, ministries, academic institutions, farmers, and industry partners. As a formal communication tool, it supports the Institute’s position as a national research organisation and serves as a reference point for official information and documentation. In parallel, KIS uses Instagram as a secondary channel, offering a more accessible format for communication with a wider audience. Instagram enables the Institute to present activities in a visual and simplified way, which can be relevant for outreach beyond professional and academic circles. In relation to seed products and bean varieties, this channel has the potential to reach groups such as hobby gardeners, small-scale producers, and consumers interested in local food systems, who represent an important segment of the domestic seed market. Overall, KIS’s media presence can be considered established but not fully developed in terms of marketing and product visibility.

4.4 Implementation of label in the organic value chain

For the Agricultural Institute of Slovenia, incorporating certification labels into the marketing of its bean seed portfolio is a key component of its emerging commercial strategy. A reliable label acts as a communication tool that connects the product's scientific and agroecological identity with the expectations of informed growers and gardeners. In the case of bean varieties, whose qualities, such as local adaptation, genetic diversity, and compatibility with organic systems, aren't immediately obvious, a credible label serves as a visible and verifiable shorthand. This shorthand helps justify both the product choice and its price.

KIS currently markets two categories of bean seed products. The first consists of KIS Bogo and KIS Deodat, registered as Organic Heterogeneous Materials (OHM) under EU Regulation 2018/848, whose label communication is governed by the OHM regulatory framework. The second consists of conventionally registered varieties, KIS Amand, KIS Marcelijan, and KIS Pavlin, which are locally adapted, open-pollinated, and bred with sustainability objectives, but have not yet been certified under an organic breeding label. These varieties are potential candidates for the bioverita OV (Organic Variety) label, subject to verification of organic breeding standard as defined by this private quality label.

Unlike the RSR case, where the OHM label is already in operational use, the KIS marketing strategy is designed as a prospective framework. The strategy has nonetheless been fully developed, so that KIS is positioned to activate it rapidly once the certification conditions are met.

The strategic orientation of this pilot is to operationalise the OV label as a market differentiation tool at the seed level. Unlike the RSR case, where labelling is attached to downstream food products, the KIS strategy functions at the upstream segment of the value chain. The label, therefore, acts directly on seed purchasing decisions by growers.

The value chain structure for the KIS pilot is defined as follows: Breeding (KIS) > Seed multiplication > Packaging and distribution > Growers (hobby gardeners and small farmers) > Food production for local consumption.

4.4.1 Connection of narrative with labels

The narratives established within the project provide a solid foundation for communicating the values behind the KIS bean portfolio. Three narrative clusters are particularly relevant across both product categories, though their application differs

from the RSR case, given the distinct context of a research institute selling seed material rather than a farm selling a food product.

Local adaptation and climate resilience.

All KIS bean varieties are developed from Slovenian germplasm that has been shaped by centuries of local cultivation and tested under Slovenian field conditions. The breeding programme is explicitly oriented toward performance under heat stress, water deficiency, and disease pressure, which are conditions characteristic of Slovenian growing seasons. The narrative translates directly into a practical argument for growers: these varieties have been calibrated for their specific environment in ways that imported commercial varieties have not.

Community building and value chain collaboration.

KIS participates in a community of researchers and breeders in Europe who share the same production philosophy. This narrative is less immediately prominent for the hobby gardening segment, for which institutional affiliation is not a primary purchase driver, and should therefore be used selectively, primarily on the website, at events where KIS researchers present their work directly, and in communication targeting organic growers.

Locality and independence from global market dynamics

The KIS breeding programme, by maintaining and improving locally adapted germplasm rather than deploying standardised international genetics, contributes to the preservation of Slovenian crop diversity and reduces growers' dependence on seed sourced from large commercial producers. For consumers and growers motivated by sustainability values, this narrative creates a connection between the individual purchasing decision and a wider commitment to food system resilience.

These narratives should be actively connected to label communication through complementary tools integrated into product packaging. As demonstrated in the LiveSeeding project's communication research, hybrid communication approaches, particularly QR codes linking physical packaging to digital content, are effective in bridging the limited information space on a seed packet and the fuller story that motivates purchase decisions among informed consumers.

In the KIS context, narratives are therefore not only translated into seed packaging communication but also into grower-facing guidance that enables downstream visibility. The operational objective is that growers using OV-certified varieties can communicate breeding origin on the bean product in short supply chains, thereby

testing whether breeding-origin information can function as a demand driver beyond the seed purchase moment.

4.4.2 Guidelines for the implementation of label based communication

Product packaging

Packaging for KIS Amand, KIS Marcelijan, and KIS Pavlin should clearly communicate their unique agronomic and nutritional strengths such as early maturation, disease resistance, and higher iron and zinc content, where applicable. However, the packaging must not imply certified organic breeding status, as this has not yet been formally established and is pending the outcome of the Bioverita OV eligibility assessment. In the KIS context, narratives are translated into seed packaging communication and grower-facing guidance that enhances downstream visibility. Once Bioverita certification is obtained for any variety, the certification label should be prominently featured on the packaging as a primary quality mark, accompanied by a brief explanation of what the certification entails. All seed packages, regardless of the variety category, should include a QR code that links to the specific variety page on the KIS website. Additionally, the packaging should display the institute's branding and contact information, along with variety-specific cultivation guidance tailored for the Slovenian hobby gardening context.

Point-of-sale and event environments

At agricultural fairs, gardening events, and KIS open days, printed variety information sheets should be available for each product. These sheets should replicate the core packaging message in an expanded format, providing a more detailed explanation of the OHM concept or the OV certification, targeting growers who stop to inquire. In retail settings, such as organic shops and specialist garden centres, KIS products should be accompanied by shelf cards or small printed materials. These should emphasize the locality narrative and the agronomic relevance, stating: "Developed for Slovenian conditions and tested at KIS's research station in Jablje."

Digital channels

When posting on social media about KIS bean products, always include a visual reference to the appropriate label. The dedicated bean varieties section of the KIS website should clearly explain the difference between OHM and OV in simple, non-technical language. It should also clarify the current certification status of each variety

and provide direct purchasing or inquiry information. This page should serve as the primary destination for QR codes on all packaging.

Bioverita OV pathway for conventionally registered varieties

KIS should initiate an eligibility assessment for the Bioverita OV label for KIS Amand, KIS Marcelijan, and KIS Pavlin. This assessment should determine whether the breeding of these varieties was conducted in line with the standard of organic plant breeding of this quality label. If eligibility is confirmed, the formal Bioverita application process should be initiated.

4.5 Marketing goal

4.5.1 Main goal

The main marketing goal for KIS over the next twelve to twenty-four months is to establish initial commercial visibility and product recognition for its bean seed portfolio in the Slovenian seed market. Given that the institute is at an early stage of commercial product development, the varieties exist and are scientifically validated, but standardised packaging, distribution infrastructure, and consumer-facing communication are not yet in place. The priority is not market expansion but market entry. The immediate objective is to create a first community of growers and gardeners who know the KIS bean portfolio, understand its differentiation from commercial alternatives, and have reliable access to purchase it.

By building a base of informed early adopters, hobby gardeners and organic growers already motivated by local origin, climate reliability, and sustainability values, KIS creates the conditions for sustainable commercial scaling in a subsequent phase, without overextending its current production and distribution capacity.

4.5.2 Specific goal

The following specific goals operationalise the main marketing objective across a twelve-to twenty-four-month timeframe:

- 1) Develop and publish a dedicated bean varieties section on the KIS website within four months, covering all five varieties with consistent product sheets, cultivation guidance for Slovenian conditions, and clear purchasing or inquiry information.
- 2) Establish a structured social media content plan for Facebook and Instagram, with a minimum of two posts per week during the gardening season, focused on variety profiles, growing tips, field photography, and event promotion. Increase engagement on bean-related content by 15% within twelve months.
- 3) Develop and produce standardised seed packaging for at least four varieties within six months, and a consistent design identity across the portfolio that supports retail placement and fair display.

- 4) Establish at least one operational distribution channel for bean seed products within twelve months, whether through direct online sales from the KIS website, a retail partnership with an organic shop or garden centre, or a consignment arrangement with a seed retailer.
- 5) Establish at least one pilot grower partnerships that agree to communicate “grown from organically bred varieties” on the final bean product in short supply chains (local markets, farm shops, or selected retail points) within 12 months.
- 6) Organise one open day at the KIS Infrastructure Centre Jablje during the growing season, inviting hobby gardeners, organic farmers, and agricultural advisors to visit the bean trial plots and interact directly with the breeding team.

4.6 Customer segment

4.6.1 Primary customer segment

The primary customer segment for KIS bean seed products consists of hobby gardeners and self-sufficient households distributed across Slovenia. Based on the interview with the KIS team, the typical buyer is aged between forty and sixty-five, grows beans as part of a broader home garden, and is primarily motivated by growing reliable, known-quality food for family consumption. This customer is not necessarily an expert in organic certification or seed systems, but is increasingly aware of food origin, willing to pay a modest premium for clearly differentiated local products, and receptive to evidence-based variety recommendations from a trusted source.

The primary segment can be further characterised along two overlapping sub-profiles:

- **Established home gardeners.** This sub-group has a long-standing gardening tradition and a strong preference for varieties they trust from experience or recommendation. They typically make seed purchases in early spring through garden centres or supermarket seed displays and are motivated primarily by growing reliability and familiar results. As noted in the institute interview, varieties that fail to perform under Slovenian summer heat generate frustration and brand switching. This sub-group responds most strongly to the local adaptation and agronomic reliability narrative, delivered through familiar channels: packaging, gardening fairs, and Facebook.
- **Informed new-generation gardeners.** This sub-group consists of adults in the thirty-five to fifty age bracket who have taken up home food production more recently, motivated by food quality, origin transparency, and sustainability. They actively research varieties online, follow gardening content on social media, and are receptive to narratives around biodiversity and ecological breeding. This sub-group is the primary audience for content-based marketing through the KIS website and Instagram, and for the more detailed aspects of the Bioverita OV story.

For both profiles, local adaptation and reliability are the dominant purchase drivers, while OV certification functions as an additional credibility and differentiation signal. The primary segment is distributed across Slovenia without strong regional concentration, as home gardening is widespread in both rural and peri-urban households. It can be reached most efficiently through Facebook, the KIS website, and

seasonal gardening events and fairs. As confirmed in the interview, specialist organic platforms are not among the primary discovery channels for this age group.

4.6.2 Secondary customer segment

The secondary customer segment includes organic and semi-organic small farms across Slovenia. This segment comprises farms operating under organic certification or transitioning toward reduced-input systems. These buyers are more technically informed than hobby gardeners. For this segment, OHM classification and Bioverita OV certification are meaningful differentiation signals because they align with the regulatory and philosophical frameworks within which organic farmers operate.

A smaller but strategically relevant sub-segment consists of seed multipliers and specialist organic seed retailers. Given the constrained production and packaging capacity of KIS, licensing or multiplication partnerships could allow the bean portfolio to reach larger distribution volumes without requiring the institute to expand its own operational footprint. This is a medium-term opportunity that becomes realistic once the varieties have established initial market recognition and the institute has developed the commercial infrastructure, packaging, purchasing processes, and logistics to support a partnership arrangement.

A third segment, relevant over the longer term, consists of agricultural extension services, advisory organisations, and educational institutions that could integrate KIS varieties into knowledge transfer programmes. As mentioned in the institute interview, demonstration plots and institutional partnerships, including open days at the Jablje research station, are an existing and valued channel through which KIS already engages with professional growers and advisors. Strengthening this channel with branded seed products and clear label communication would allow KIS to leverage its institutional credibility to build the professional grower segment alongside the hobby gardening market.

4.7 Key messages – narratives

The key messages for KIS's bean seed marketing strategy are derived from the project's communication framework established in T6.1 and adapted to the specific context of the institute and its products. Each message is formulated to address both the practical motivations of growers who want reliable, locally adapted seed and the values-based motivations of buyers engaged with biodiversity, sustainability, and food sovereignty, in line with the evidence that combined approaches produce stronger consumer engagement. The messages cover the full KIS portfolio and are calibrated to reflect the two product categories: registered OHM varieties (KIS Bogo and KIS Deodat) and conventionally registered varieties with OV potential (KIS Amand, KIS Marcelijan, KIS Pavlin).

The following messages are proposed as illustrative examples of grower- and consumer-facing communication content, developed to demonstrate how the narrative clusters identified in T6.1 can be operationalised within KIS's specific market context (Figure 18).

Figure 18 Key messages for KIS and connection with LiveSeeding communication narratives (D6.1)

Message 1: Bred from Slovenian seeds, tested in Slovenian fields (Narrative cluster: local adaptation and climate resilience)

“These bean varieties were developed from Slovenian seed and tested in Slovenian fields. They are calibrated for the specific conditions of Slovenian soil, climate, and growing seasons. When you plant a KIS variety, you are planting something that already knows this land.” This message communicates the local origin of the portfolio as a practical growing advantage and is the unifying narrative across all five varieties. It should appear consistently on packaging, at fairs, and in all social media content.

Message 2: Reliable where it matters (Narrative cluster: local adaptation and climate resilience)

“KIS Marcelijan matures early, before the worst of the summer heat arrives. KIS Amand resists the diseases that damage conventional varieties in wet seasons. KIS Pavlin produces both fresh pods and dry beans from the same plant. These are not catalogue claims; they are documented results from years of field trials at Jablje.” This message translates the breeding programme's scientific outputs into grower-relevant language, grounding variety performance in specific, verifiable claims. It is most effective on variety product sheets, on the KIS website, and in communication targeting organic farmers and technically informed gardeners.

Message 3: More than 120 years of research expertise behind every seed
(Narrative cluster: community building and value chain collaboration)

“The Agricultural Institute of Slovenia has been developing cultivars for Slovenian agriculture for over 120 years. When KIS says a variety tolerates drought or resists anthracnose, that claim is backed by documented field trials and accredited laboratory analysis. You are buying decades of applied research.” This message addresses the credibility dimension of the KIS brand, distinguishing it from commercial seed companies that communicate primarily on variety names and packaging imagery. It is suitable for use at events and open days, on the website's institutional section, and in communication with the organic farming segment, which is most likely to evaluate and value the research foundation.

Message 4: Part of a living seed heritage *(Narrative cluster: locality and independence from global market dynamics)*

“Every KIS variety carries genetics shaped by centuries of Slovenian cultivation. Choosing one is a contribution to the continuity of local agricultural diversity, to a food system that does not depend entirely on seeds designed and controlled elsewhere. KIS is part of a European network of researchers and breeders working toward the same goal.” This message connects the individual purchase to a wider set of values around food sovereignty, biodiversity, and sustainable agriculture. It is most relevant as a secondary layer of communication, available on the website and in event presentations for those who seek it, and is best suited to the organic farming segment and the informed new-generation gardener sub-profile rather than to price-sensitive buyers for whom it functions as a distraction from the core agronomic message.

4.8 Channels

The selection of marketing channels for KIS (Table 5) is guided by the access patterns of the target segments, the institute's current communication infrastructure, and the operational constraints identified in the interview. Facebook and the KIS website are prioritised as primary digital channels, as these are the platforms through which the primary segment of hobby gardeners and small farmers most commonly discover and engage with agricultural content. Instagram serves as a secondary visual channel for the younger segment and for showcasing the visual diversity of KIS bean varieties. Physical channels, particularly agricultural and gardening fairs and open days at the KIS Infrastructure Centre Jablje, are especially important in the initial market entry phase because they allow direct explanation of OHM and Bioverita concepts that are not yet widely understood by the primary segment. Retail partnerships with organic shops and garden centres represent a medium-term distribution target, to be pursued once packaging and purchasing processes are standardised.

Table 5 List of media channels and their description for Agricultural Institute of Slovenia (KIS)

Channel	Description
KIS website	Primary institutional channel and central hub for product information. To be expanded with a dedicated bean varieties section, including individual variety pages, cultivation guidance, and a purchasing or inquiry function. All QR codes on packaging should link to this platform.
Facebook	Primary social media channel for the core target segment of hobby gardeners aged 40+. As confirmed in the interview, Facebook currently performs best among KIS's existing platforms for this demographic. Recommended for regular content during the gardening season, variety profiles, growing tips, field photography, and event promotion.
Instagram	Secondary visual channel suited for showcasing variety diversity, field photography from Jablje, and reaching the younger informed gardener segment. To be used in parallel with Facebook with adapted content formats.
KIS Infrastructure Centre Jablje	Key experiential channel for direct engagement with hobby gardeners, organic farmers, and agricultural advisors. As confirmed in the interview, direct contact at events is the most effective way to communicate product differentiation. Open days allow visitors to see trial plots, interact with the breeding team, and receive seed take-home materials.
Agricultural and gardening fairs	Physical channel for reaching the primary segment at the point of seasonal seed purchasing decisions. Booth presence with finalised packaging, printed variety materials, and staff prepared to explain OHM and Bioverita in an accessible language.
Webshop / online sales	Identified in the interview as a desired future channel. Economic viability requires careful consideration of delivery cost relative to seed package price. To be evaluated as part of the distribution channel activation activity, with a minimum order model as a potential solution.
Retail partnerships	Medium-term distribution target. Organic shops and specialist garden centres in Ljubljana and other Slovenian cities represent the most relevant retail environment for KIS's premium and sustainability-positioned product portfolio. To be activated once packaging is standardised.
LinkedIn	Currently active at the institutional level. Less relevant for the hobby gardening segment but useful for reaching agricultural professionals, advisors, and potential seed multiplier partners.
TikTok	Identified in the interview as a potential future channel for educational content aimed at younger audiences and for promoting agriculture as a career. Not recommended as a priority in the current phase due to resource constraints, but worth monitoring as the platform's demographic broadens.

4.9 Suggested activities

These activities are derived from the stakeholder interviews and analysis presented in previous sections and serve to operationalise the proposed marketing strategy into concrete actions.

Activity 1: Seed packaging and product identity development

Design and produce a standardised seed packaging system for the KIS bean portfolio. All packages should include KIS branding and a QR code linking to the variety page on the KIS website. In parallel, develop a variety product sheet for each variety in print and digital format. This activity is the prerequisite for all distribution and sales activities.

Activity 2: KIS website bean varieties section

Develop and publish a dedicated bean varieties section on the KIS website, covering all five varieties with individual product pages, an accessible introduction to the Common Bean Breeding Programme, and a practical purchasing or inquiry page. Each variety page should present the agronomic profile, key cultivation guidance for Slovenian conditions, and the relevant sustainability narrative. The QR codes on physical packaging should link directly to these pages. Website content should be available in Slovenian as the primary language. This activity supports all other distribution and communication activities and should be completed within the first four months.

Activity 3: Structured content on Facebook and Instagram

Establish a structured content calendar for Facebook as the primary channel and Instagram as secondary, aligned with the Slovenian gardening season and maintainable within the institute's available communication capacity. Key content moments should include variety introductions and pre-sowing guidance in February and March; growing season updates, field photography from Jablje, and cultivation tips from May to August; harvest guidance and culinary content in September and October; and institutional credibility content and research news in the winter months. Content should rotate between five recurring themes: variety profiles, field process, growing tips, researcher perspectives, and event promotion. The OHM designation and Bioverita label, if it will be certified in the future, should appear consistently in visual content to build recognition.

Activity 4: Open day at the Infrastructure Centre Jablje

Organise one open day at the KIS Infrastructure Centre Jablje during the growing season, with June or September recommended as the most agronomically informative timing for the bean crop. The event should be designed as a direct interface between the institute's breeding work and its primary target audience of hobby gardeners, organic growers, and agricultural advisors. Programme elements should include guided visits to the bean trial plots, presentations by the breeding team on variety

characteristics and the OHM concept, physical demonstration of variety diversity, and a seed take-home option for participants. The event should be documented with photographs and short video content for subsequent use across social media and the website.

Activity 5: Participation in a national agricultural or gardening fair

Prepare and execute a KIS bean variety booth presence at at least one national agricultural or gardening event. The booth should present seed packages in finalised packaging, printed variety materials, and visual documentation of the trial plots. As confirmed in the institute interview, direct contact with growers at fairs is currently the most effective channel for communicating product differentiation.

Activity 6: Distribution channel activation and Bioverita pathway

Activate at least one operational distribution channel for bean seed products by month twelve. The options to evaluate are: direct online sales from the KIS website, with a minimum order model to address delivery economics for seed packages in the EUR 3–6 price range; a consignment partnership with one or two retail points – organic shops or garden centres in Ljubljana or other Slovenian cities; or a seed network partnership allowing multiplication and distribution without requiring KIS to expand its own logistics. In parallel, initiate the Bioverita OV eligibility assessment for the conventionally registered varieties within the first three months, and proceed to formal Bioverita application within six months if eligibility is confirmed. Once certification is obtained, communicate it as a quality milestone through a press release and a social media announcement.

4.10 Matrix of activities

The activities (Table 6) are structured to follow a logical progression in which preparatory elements are completed before more visible market-facing actions begin. Packaging development, the website bean section, and the social media content programme are prioritised in the first four to six months because they form the communication foundation on which all subsequent activities depend. Distribution channel activation, fair participation, and the Bioverita pathway are sequenced to follow once this foundation is in place, ensuring that KIS enters each new channel with consistent and professional product communication already established.

Progress of the KPIs should be reviewed at six-month intervals. Since structured marketing measurement is not currently part of KIS's operational practice, it is recommended that a basic tracking system be established from the outset: website analytics and QR code scan data per variety page, engagement metrics on bean-related social media content, and a simple record of open day attendance, fair contacts, and distribution inquiries received. Building this process of measurement from the beginning will allow the strategy to be adjusted on the basis of evidence.

Table 6 Matrix of activities for Agricultural Institute of Slovenia (KIS)

Activity	Timeline	Responsible	KPI / Expected output
1: Seed packaging and product identity development	M1–M6	KIS breeding team + communication	Production-ready packaging for 4–5 varieties by M6; variety product sheets published in print and digital format
2: KIS website bean varieties section	M2–M4	KIS communication team	Section live with individual variety pages and QR codes active; purchasing or inquiry page functional
3: Structured content programme on Facebook and Instagram	M1–M24 (ongoing)	KIS communication team	Content calendar documented and active; minimum 2 posts/week on Facebook during gardening season (March–September); 15% engagement increase on bean content within 12 months
4: Open day at Infrastructure Centre Jablje	M6–M9	KIS breeding team + administration	40+ participants; event documented with photos and short video; content published within one week of event
5: Participation in national agricultural or gardening fair	M6–M12	KIS breeding team + communication	Booth presence at Agra Gornja Radgona or equivalent; seed samples distributed; direct consumer contacts documented
6: Distribution channel activation and Bioverita pathway	M1–M3 (assessment); M3–M6 (Bioverita contact); M6–M12 (distribution)	KIS administration + breeding team	At least one distribution channel operational by M12; Bioverita eligibility confirmed or transition pathway defined by M6

5. Conclusions & Recommendations

This deliverable examines how dedicated labels can serve as market differentiation for products derived from the new organic cultivar types (OV and OHM) and how the LiveSeeding Communication narratives (D6.1) can be operationalised through specific communication tools, channels, and activities.

Key findings

In both pilot cases, the value generated by organic breeding and diversity-based seed systems is largely invisible at the point of purchase. The **OHM and bioverita labels** alone do not convey their full meaning without active narrative support. Each label acts as an entry point into a broader story that must be told across multiple complementary channels (packaging, digital content, direct outreach, events). This multi-channel narrative approach is essential because the value proposition (sustainability, biodiversity, taste, etc.) is complex and not self-evident.

A second common finding is the critical role of interpersonal channels. In the RSR (FURAT) case, a small organic farm selling pasta in a premium, short-chain market, the most powerful marketing was direct consumer engagement (hospitality events, tastings), not just social media or label text. In the KIS case, a public research institute promoting OHM seeds to growers, open days and agricultural fairs were the most effective means to explain the OHM concept and the benefits of locally adapted breeding. In both, personal contact-built trust and understanding far more than passive media.

Regarding replicability, the RSR strategy is a model for other small farms/processors using OHM in short supply chains; the KIS strategy provides a template for research organizations and breeding institutes that have proven varieties but lack a retail presence. From a policy standpoint, both cases affirm that regulatory recognition of OV/OHM (e.g. via Reg. 2021/1189) is necessary but not sufficient for market uptake. There is a gap between legal recognition and economic viability that must be bridged by communication, certification, and value-chain cooperation. In practice, label-based strategies (like those here) are one concrete way to strengthen that bridge.

It should also be noted that the communication tools and activities proposed in both strategies are intentionally drawn from established practice rather than experimental formats. This reflects a deliberate methodological choice: the primary innovation of this deliverable lies not in the novelty of individual communication instruments, but in the application of a structured, label-based marketing framework to a product category for which such frameworks have not previously existed in a systematic form.

Replicability by resource-constrained actors was prioritised over communicative experimentation.

Finally, both strategies point toward a broader take home message for the LiveSeeding project and for future initiatives in this space: the development of transferable communication tools and templates that can reduce the individual burden on small actors. Sun Agricoltura and KIS each face the challenge of communicating complex concepts with limited resources. Shared narrative frameworks, standardised label implementation guidelines, and collective communication infrastructure, such as those developed through the RSR network and the bioverita association, reduce duplication of effort and strengthen the coherence of OV and OHM communication across the European organic sector

Key Recommendations

Recommendation 1. Integrate the label into a broader narrative package and support it consistently across packaging, digital content, and events. The label itself is just a signal; without narrative context its meaning (for biodiversity, resilience, etc.) is unclear.

Recommendation 2. Prioritise interpersonal channels (tastings, open farms, fairs) as core activities and use digital media to amplify them. For complex, unfamiliar value propositions, direct experience and explanation build trust faster than passive channels. Both case studies show that face-to-face engagement (e.g. farm events, field days) is crucial to convert interest into understanding, mirroring Bioverita's emphasis on education along the value chain.

Recommendation 3. Segment communication by value-chain position and audience (B2C storytelling vs. B2B technical trust). Downstream consumers need messages about taste, health, and ethical impact; upstream actors need evidence of performance and credibility. The RSR (consumer food) and KIS (seed provider) cases require different tones and proofs of value for their respective customers.

Recommendation 4. Establish minimal label governance (claim rules, usage agreements, verification) before launch. Without clear rules, partners see reputational risk. Bioverita requires producers to sign a use agreement and undergo audits (four-yearly + annual update). Similar transparency and verification steps should be defined so retailers and consumers trust the label.

Recommendation 5. Develop transferable communication tools and templates at the project level to reduce the burden on small actors. SMEs and public breeders often lack marketing capacity. Shared assets (standard text, visuals, FAQ, demo itineraries) like those used by the bioverita network make campaigns scalable and coherent (for example, bioverita's standardized label claims and communication guidelines)

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Annex 1

Overview of the interview conducted to collect key insights for the development of pilot marketing strategies.

Company overview
How would you briefly describe the company (mission, vision, values)?
History of the company
The company's core activities
Key milestones in the company's development
Final product
Product overview (core features, role in overall business)
What role does the type of cultivar (OHM /OV) play in the final product features?
What role do the general organic label and the OV label play in the product features?
What role does agroecology play in your final product?
What core problem does this product solve, and for whom?
What do you want this product to achieve in the next 12-24 months?
SWOT analysis
What are the main strengths compared to competitors, and which internal resources or capabilities give you a competitive advantage?
What internal challenges and limitations does the company face, and what areas of the business need improvement?
What market trends represent opportunities for your business, and are there new markets or customer segments you want to explore?
What external factors could negatively impact your business, and how do competitors or market changes threaten your position?
Competition analysis
Who are your main direct and indirect competitors at the local level?
How are competitors positioned (price, quality, brand image)?
How do you differentiate yourself from the competitors?
How does the circular and short food supply chain differentiate you from your competitors?
How does the type of cultivar (OV/OHM) from which the product derives influence your positioning compared to the competitors?
USP (Unique Selling Proposition) of the product
Why should customers choose your product? /What makes you different from others?
What customer problem do you solve better than others?
How do you currently communicate your USP (the attributes that distinguish your product)?
Media presence
Which media and platforms are you currently present on?
How often do you publish content?
Are there any channels you would like to use or wouldn't like?
Which channels perform best and why? (If applicable)

Customer segment
Who is your ideal customer?
What are the key demographic characteristics of your customers?
How do your primary and secondary customer segments differ?
What are the main needs, problems, or motivations of your customers?
Channels (current and potential)
Through which channels do customers most often find you?
Which channels generate the most leads or sales?
How do you measure the effectiveness of each channel? (KEY METRICS)
Marketing goals (main and specific)
What are your main marketing goals for the next 6–12 months?
Is your focus more on brand awareness, lead generation, or sales?
Do you have specific, measurable goals (e.g., revenue growth, leads, or followers)?
Which markets or customer segments are a priority?
How important is the local value chain to your products in your marketing strategy?
Use of the label
What is / can be the role of the OHM RSR/ bioverita label in the marketing of your product?
What are the opportunities and challenges of using the RSR OHM/bioverita OV label for marketing your product?
How important is the general organic production label for your marketing strategy?
Is there any other label that could be used to support the marketing of your product?